

**WP1 – Scoping and Framing of pathways
towards SFS**

D1.1: Conceptual Framework

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List of abbreviations

CAP – Common Agriculture Policy
CF - conceptual framework
EC – European Commission
GA – Grant Agreement
MLP - multilevel perspective
SFS – Sustainable farming system
WP – Work package

1 Executive summary

The ENFASYS conceptual framework is an important guide for conducting the research in the project, by introducing important concepts of the research topic under investigation, by defining how these concepts are related, and by shaping interactions between different teams and work packages within the project. The conceptual framework provides a coherent work that supports the combined consideration of (1) **systems thinking** on **lock-ins** and levers in **farming and food systems** that prevent transitions to more SFS; (2) **behavioural factors** affecting farmers-adoption of more SFS; (3) **public interventions** such as policies in the CAP, and agricultural and environmental policies in the member states and; (4) **private interventions** such as business strategies and social innovations – to move farmers to more SFS.

Figure 1 is a graphical representation of the ENFASYS conceptual framework. The first elements are the behavioural factors and systemic factors that have been identified as key elements enabling or hindering change toward sustainable farming systems (SFS). **Behavioural factors** refer to elements that relate to the capacity and motivations of individuals, such as farmers, buyers, citizens, investors to make decisions. It encompasses the whole range of factors that are to be considered in order to understand these decisions. **Systemic factors** are those constraining and motivating effects on individuals' actions of social dynamics of the systems or social structures in which actors are positioned. These systems consist out of social relationships between different actors, that constrain, enable and motivate actors depending on their position in various ways.

Figure 1: ENFASYS conceptual framework

We identified the **multilevel perspective (MLP) on sustainability transitions** as a powerful heuristic that provides key concepts potentially enabling to link behavioural and systemic perspectives in a single narrative for the project. At its core, the MLP describes the transition towards sustainability of different socio-technical systems by conceptualising them as a regime change induced by the scaling up of radical niche innovations. The MLP itself is a systemic perspective which does not explicitly address behavioural factors, but it does have the ability to pay attention to micro-level agency at the niche level, while still considering meso-level and macro-level dynamics and interactions between these multiple levels. On this basis, we've formed the hypothesis that the MLP can provide the broader framework to link the behavioural and systemic factors in the transition towards SFS.

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ENFASYS aims at creating knowledge relevant to enable the transition towards SFS. The concept of **three types of knowledge** distinguishes the knowledge needed to generate change through a research project. First **system knowledge** refers to knowledge about “what is”, that is the current situation about an issue. **Target knowledge**, defines how the system should look like in order to be sustainable. And finally, **transformation knowledge** focuses on how to get from the current to the desired situation. The three types of knowledge are all needed to understand **public and private interventions** which have already happened in farming systems, as well as to inform the design interventions design within ENFASYS to enable behavioural or systemic change. The interventions are the pivotal point between knowledge production within ENFASYS and its real-world impact.

The interdisciplinary nature of the ENFASYS project as well as the aim to bring together research traditions that share very different assumptions reinforces the need to develop a common language to enable collaboration, but also comparison and generalization across the different teams and work packages of the project. To do so, the concepts used in the CF need to be clearly defined, yet broad enough so that partners from different background can understand, but also make use of them. Therefore, we developed a glossary defining the main concepts, but also other related terms and concepts, to enable a common understanding.

2 Introduction

The ENFASYS project aims to stimulate a just and robust transition to sustainable, productive, climate-neutral, biodiversity friendly and resilient farming systems by improved policies and business strategies that encourage farmers to change their production systems.

In this deliverable, we introduce the conceptual framework (CF) of the project. A conceptual framework is “a network of interlinked concepts that together provide a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon or phenomena” (Jabareen, 2009). As such, the conceptual framework is an important guide for conducting the research. It directs towards specific aspects of the research topic under investigation. It also shapes interactions between different teams and work packages within the project, as it defines how different concepts important for the project are related.

In this introduction, we present the ENFASYS-CF, its aims and scopes and the process through which it was developed. In the following sections we then elaborate on the key concepts that constitute the different building blocks of the CF. This is followed by a glossary that defines these key concepts, as well as secondary concepts relevant to project work.

2.1 Aims and scope of the ENFASYS-CF

The CF presented here forms the theoretical underpinning for activities within the project that support meeting the project’s aim. This subsection details what the CF is and its purposes for ENFASYS.

2.1.1 Relating multiple concepts to seize a complex reality

The transformation of farming systems is characteristic of sustainability problems encountered at global level, but demanding differentiated answers at local level. Sustainability problems are complex phenomena that often require the collaboration of multiple academic disciplines as well as the active involvement of non-academic research partners in order to be tackled in an effective way (Dentoni et al., 2017; Pearce & Ejderyan, 2020). Because of this complex and interconnected nature, sustainability problems always relate to broader systems that need to be considered when conducting analytical work to develop solutions.

In order to get to the complexity of such problems, it is necessary to abstract some of their features. Such abstractions occur through concepts. Concepts are notions that isolate selected elements of a phenomenon and bring them together in order to understand this phenomenon. As such, concepts are purposive. What they focus on, isolate, or relate, is always guided by a problem that the concept can help to address. Therefore, concepts are flexible constructs, and when part of a framework, they create relations and distinctions between parts of reality. Because they are abstractions, concepts can travel between disciplines, theories, etc., each time generating new questions. As such, concepts “resist time and space and produce a renewed relevance in circumstances that have yet to be determined” (Stengers, 2011, p. 327) As they apply to real world phenomena that share some of the elements abstracted but are yet different, concepts also allow for comparison, distinction or generalization. As an example, a concept such as sustainable farming system (SFS), that is key to ENFASYS enables to analyse together different farming systems that share the feature of being sustainable, but that might be so in various ways. It also enables to distinguish sustainable from unsustainable farming systems.

Concepts are tools. They offer a common language to talk about complex object/phenomena we look at. They are abstract representations of these objects that enable us to seize and understand part of them. Yet, because they are abstract (and representations) they are always incomplete. As such dealing with them is not straightforward. They enable us to talk the same language, but do not necessarily create agreement.

In order to research complex phenomena such as sustainability issues, it is necessary to relate to multiple concepts. These concepts might apply to different real-world aspects of the phenomenon studied. But they might also shed light on a same aspect from different disciplinary or theoretical perspectives.

It is through a CF that the relationship between various concepts is organized (and visualized). A CF is therefore not a loose compilation of concepts, nor a graph showing all possible relationships between concepts. Jabareen (2009) distinguishes several features of a CF that inform the ENFASYS CF. First, a CF is a purposeful construct in which “each concept plays an integral role” (Jabareen, 2009, p. 51). It does not provide a causal explanation of the relationships between the concepts, but rather points towards relationships that still need to be examined and

explained. A CF rather provides “soft interpretation of intentions” (Levering, cited in Jabareen, 2009) rather than facts. A CF is indeterminist in nature and does not offer any predictions.

2.1.2 Requirements to the ENFASYS-CF

Based on the above definitions, the CF should give guidance on WHAT to study within the ENFASYS project. In contrast to the methodological framework (T4.1), aiming at giving guidance on HOW to study it. The conceptual framework will nonetheless make reference to methodologies and analytical frameworks that will be used in the project, for what purpose (e.g. to examine or create a certain phenomenon) and the levels of analysis or action (CS, regional/national/European).

The ENFASYS Grant Agreement set the goal “to develop a tailored systems-based conceptual framework to facilitate a holistic analysis of the different research activities, with consideration of different levels of analysis; the proposed interventions; and the conducted experiments that contribute to ENFASYS objectives. The conceptual framework provide a coherent work that supports the combined consideration of (1) **systemic lock-ins** and levers in **farming and food systems** that prevent or may enable transitions to more SFS; (2) **behavioural factors** affecting farmers’ adoption of more SFS; (3) **public interventions** such as policies in the CAP, and agricultural and environmental policies in the members states and; (4) **private interventions** such as business strategies and social innovations – to move farmers to more SFS”. It is with this background that the initial concepts characterizing the ENFASYS approach were selected.

Further, the interdisciplinary nature of the ENFASYS project as well as the aim to bring together research traditions that share very different assumptions (i.e. behavioural and systemic approaches) reinforces the need to develop a common language to enable collaboration, but also comparison and generalization across the different teams and work packages of the project. To do so, the concepts used in the CF need to be clearly defined, yet broad enough so that partners from different background can understand, but also make use of them. Therefore, we developed a glossary defining the main concepts, but also other related terms and concepts, to enable a common understanding. These shared definitions of concepts will be used throughout the project. Yet, because they are abstract (and representations) the concepts of the CF do not encompass the full reality of the phenomena we study. As such, dealing with them is not straightforward. So, while they enable us to talk the same language and work on the same issues, they do not necessarily create “agreement”.

The ENFASYS CF should facilitate a holistic analysis of the different research activities, with consideration of different levels of analysis; the proposed interventions; and the conducted experiments. The CF sets boundaries to make the project coherent, while allowing for maximum freedom and flexibility for the partners. The idea is to create a framework that is sufficiently broad that all the work in ENFASYS can find a place within it, but also sufficiently narrow that it enables comparisons and generalisations.

2.2 Overview of the ENFASYS-CF

To develop the ENFASYS-CF we used different sources to select the key concepts, identify theoretical approaches to relate them, and finally build a framework that will enable the various research teams within the project’s work package to reach the goals set in the grant agreement.

The grant agreement was taken as an initial input, providing key concepts and research questions to orient the construction of the CF. It set the initial challenge, namely that of developing a conceptual framework enabling to link research on behavioural factors with research on systemic factors to transition to SFS.

This was followed by exchanges and discussion within the WP1 team to identify suitable approaches. From these discussions, we identified the Multilevel Perspective (MLP) as an existing analytical framework that offers potential to build a conceptual framework that links systemic and behavioural factors (see chapter 2 and section 4.4). We then identified the three type of knowledge approach from transdisciplinary research as a tool to create interventions-relevant knowledge from the analytical work done in ENFASYS (see section 6.2 for details). We validated these initial choices with the consortium partners during a workshop dedicated to the CF at the ENFASYS General assembly meeting in Paris in February 2023.

In parallel, we conducted 4 literature reviews on system dynamics (see chapter 4), behavioural factors (see chapter 5), public interventions and private interventions (see chapter 7), that enabled us to identify key questions and concepts to guide the ENFASYS research and consolidate the framework.

Going through this process enabled us to select and organise the different building blocks of the ENFASYS conceptual framework (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The ENFASYS Conceptual Framework.

The first elements of this framework are provided by the ENFASYS grant agreement. They consist of behavioural factors and systemic factors that have been identified as key elements enabling or hindering change toward sustainable farming systems (SFS).

Behavioural factors refer to elements that relate to the capacity and motivations of individuals, such as farmers, buyers, citizens, investors to make decisions. It encompasses the whole range of factors that are to be taken into account in order to understand these decisions. These factors vary depending on the theoretical approach used. However, they generally encompass elements such as knowledge, perceptions, habits, attitude, experience, norms and values. The way these behavioural factors influence decision making or factors within sustainable farming system is also highly dependent on physical factors (size of the farm, income...) or environmental factors.

Systemic factors are those constraining and motivating effects on individuals' actions that result from social dynamics of the systems or social structures in which actors are positioned. These systems consist out of social relationships between different actors, that constrain, enable and motivate actors depending on their position in various ways (materially, cognitively, spiritually, ...). Through this 'structured' agency, actors set collectively in motion dynamics reproducing or changing the existing social relationships, and thus the systemic factors over time. Persistent systemic factors leading to undesirable patterns of behaviour are called (systemic) **lock-ins**. The term system may seek to capture phenomena at a micro-level, such as the family farm, at a meso-level like an innovation hub or a value chain, but also macro-level phenomena like global capitalism or the European Monetary Union.

ENFASYS aims to understand and intervene on these two categories of factors to move towards SFS. A key challenge of the project is to link behavioural and systemic approaches to create relevant knowledge for the transformation of current farming systems.

From the literature reviews as well as project internal consultations and discussions, we identified the **multilevel perspective (MLP) on sustainability transitions** (Geels, 2002) as a powerful heuristic that provides key concepts potentially enabling to link behavioural and systemic perspectives in a single narrative for the project. At its core, the

MLP describes the transition towards sustainability of different socio-technical systems by conceptualising them as a regime change induced by the scaling up of radical niche innovations (see section 4.4 for a detailed description). Whereas the MLP is a systemic perspective, primarily used to address systemic factors, several authors (Geels, 2020; Huttunen et al., 2021a; Morrissey et al., 2014) interested in behavioral factors have noted its ability to also pay attention to micro-level agency, albeit mostly at the niche level, while still considering meso-level and macro-level dynamics and interactions between these multiple levels. On this basis, we've formed the hypothesis that the MLP may provide the broader framework in the ENFASYS project to link the behavioural and systemic factors in the transition towards SFS. In section 6 we show through which interlinking concepts this can be achieved. The methodological framework developed in WP4 establishes the connection between these two categories of factors empirically.

As the goal of ENFASYS is to enable the transition towards SFS, it aims to create knowledge relevant to reaching this goal. The concept of **three types of knowledge** (Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007, chapter 7) distinguishes the knowledge needed to generate change through a research project. First **system knowledge** refers to knowledge about "what is", that is the current situation about an issue. **Target knowledge**, defines how the system should look like in order to be sustainable. And finally, **transformation knowledge** focuses on how to get from the current to the desired situation.

The three types of knowledge are all needed to understand **public and private interventions** which have already happened in farming systems, as well as to inform the design interventions design within ENFASYS to enable behavioural or systemic change. The interventions are the pivotal point between knowledge production within ENFASYS and its real-world impact.

Successful interventions contribute to **sustainable farming systems**, that is the target to be reached by the project.

The following chapters detail each of the above steps of the conceptual framework. In chapter 3 we first locate the ENFASYS project within current discussions on transition and transformation towards sustainability. Chapter 4 introduces the main issues regarding system dynamics in agri-food research while chapter 5 does the same with research on behavioural factors. In chapter 6, we detail how we intend to integrate interdisciplinary knowledge through the MLP and the three types of knowledge approach. Chapter 7 discusses challenges of developing public and private interventions.

3 Conceptualizing change towards SFS in ENFASYS

The goal of ENFASYS is to enable “a just and fair transition” towards “sustainable, productive, climate-neutral, biodiversity friendly and resilient farming systems (SFS)”. To achieve this goal, ENFASYS goes beyond farm level by analysing and shaping the whole value chain and overarching governance. Thus, it follows a systems approach and can be embedded in the scholarly debate surrounding the concepts of sustainability transition and transformation. Due to the complex, uncertain, and complex nature of the sustainability issues at hand, this research field is highly inter- and transdisciplinary. This might explain why the terms transition and transformation remain fuzzy and contested. Thus, diverse meanings and concepts need to be made explicit and targeted towards ENFASYS to define and delimit its purpose and modus operandi.

Figure 3: Classification of transformation concepts (adapted from Feola, 2015).

Transition and **transformation** are the two main terms to conceptualise change towards sustainability in current scholarly and policy debates. These two terms are commonly used but definitions and interpretations vary. Different attempts have been made to differentiate transition and transformation, with different schools of thought using different perspectives and approaches (Feola, 2015; Hölscher et al., 2018; Weber et al., 2020). Most scholars define transitions as more bounded, more incremental and less radical than transformations (Stirling, 2015). Pelling (2011, p. 74) identifies “transformation as an extreme case where profound change alters the distribution of rights and responsibilities and visions of development across society”, and Weber et al.,(2020, p. 12) “[see] a strong role for social movements and civil society”, allowing for agency and deliberation. Geels & Schot (2007) define transformation as one of four distinct transition pathways. While it can involve contestation and social movements pressuring incumbent actors, the regime transforms due to “cumulative adjustments” rather than a disruption of the system’s basic structure – in contrast to the understanding of the previous authors. Generally, conceptualisations in the scientific literature are either fuzzy or non-existing.

Conceptual plurality has opportunities as well as drawbacks (Feola, 2015). Feola (2015) distinguishes between two main types of research approaches: a descriptive-analytical and a solution-oriented approach¹. The latter is applicable for ENFASYS, as the project actively attempts to stimulate change towards SFS through co-designing policies, business strategies, and social innovations. The solutions-oriented approach places more emphasis on deliberate processes of change, allowing for systemic change management and including an active role of academia. Furthermore, solution-oriented research applies prescriptive concepts of transformation, which entail a desirable outcome. In the ENFASYS project, both the interpretation of SFS as well as potential pathways towards SFS are contested. Thus,

¹ Feola (2015) makes this argument for concepts surrounding the term *transformation*. As a clear distinction between *transformation* and *transition* is often lacking in the scientific literature and a focus on either of these terms would not capture the diversity of change covered in ENFASYS, Feola’s distinction of research approaches is applied to any process of change.

creativity and the wide involvement of actors are crucial, which allows for a looser definition of concepts. This vagueness can encourage action because it gives space to construct a common ground for participation. On the other hand, it might hinder transdisciplinary processes and give powerful decision-makers wanting to preserve the status quo the chance to co-opt the concept (Feola, 2015).

Conceptualising change processes towards SFS in ENFASYS has two main implications. Firstly, we cannot rely on any consensus in the scientific literature on terminology and concepts surrounding transition and transformation. Therefore, it is essential to not use these terms in a self-explanatory manner but making the underlying assumptions and concepts explicit. In order to create a shared terminology among research partners, we follow the common interpretation in the academic debate by using transition for more (sectorally) bounded and incremental processes by introducing and advancing innovations in a currently dominant system, whereas transformation indicates a more radical and contested process aiming to reconfigure the underlying structure of a system. Thus, transformative processes emphasise aspects of socio-ecological justice and open up space for the agency of individuals and collectives, disagreements and deliberation. Concepts of transformation are essential when aiming at stimulating a “just and robust transition” as it is formulated in the DoA. Secondly, conceptualising ENFASYS as solution-oriented research implies that it i) uses prescriptive concepts by striving towards a desirable outcome i.e SFS and ii) emphasises deliberate processes of change by aiming to link knowledge to action by co-designing policy mixes, business strategies, and social innovations together with stakeholders, and testing them through experiments.

The conceptually plural, prescriptive, and deliberate nature of ENFASYS necessitates transparency regarding underlying assumptions, meanings, and concepts. The process of co-creating change builds on connecting theory and practice, and including diverse actors’ perspectives. Thus, diverse and potentially contradicting perspectives exist among consortium members as well as practitioners, resulting in different (suggestions for) transition or transformation pathways. Thus, it is essential to identify and analyse personal and collective concepts throughout the project in order to compare and differentiate these pathways.

4 Systemic factors and SFS

This section focuses on the role of systemic factors in the transition towards sustainable farming systems. As hinted in the introduction, the complex nature of sustainability challenges as well as the complexity of relationships characterizing farming systems, require understanding dynamic interactions among multiple interdependent social and ecological actors through systems thinking (Dentoni et al., 2023).

4.1 Literature review

For this purpose, we reviewed the literature on system dynamics in food and agricultural research. The system dynamics review encompasses 160 papers published between 2000 and 2022². We retrieved 1591 papers on WoS and 1712 on Scopus. We removed 1021 duplicates. We screened the abstracts of the 2282 remaining references to decide for inclusion or exclusion in the review process, using the following criteria:

1. **Criteria 1 (focus on the farming/agricultural system).** We include only papers if the abstract explicitly mentions the farming/agriculture level.
2. **Criteria 2 (level).**
 - 2.1. Only include papers about case studies or a single technology if the abstract makes some generalisation/mentions the relevance of their finding for the whole system.
 - 2.2. Papers look into elements of the system and interrelations between these elements

² We searched for publication in Web of Science and Scopus using following search string: (sustainab* OR agroecolog* OR organic* OR ("biodiversity friendly" OR biodivers*) OR resilien* OR regenerat* OR holistic*) AND (agriculture* OR farm* OR food) AND system* AND (dynamic* OR mechanism* OR lock-in* OR driver* OR enable* OR lever* OR bottleneck* OR barrier* OR “path dependenc*”) AND (transition* OR transformation* OR pathway* OR trajector*)

3. **Criteria 3 (definition system dynamics)** Include papers which describe a significant change/transformation process within a food/agricultural system (both towards more sustainability and away). Papers that describe a static system and do not report or propose changes are not included.
4. **Exclusion criteria:** Study is outside of Europe, does not focus (enough) on agriculture (excl. fisheries or forestry), too technology/natural science focused, not about change toward sustainability

The screening involved 5 core reviewers from 4 partner organisations. Each abstract was screened by 2 reviewers from 2 different organisations. In case of conflict, the abstract was screened by a third reviewer and the decision to include or exclude was made on a majority basis.

Two persons reviewed the papers, with special attention put on understanding how authors conceive of systems and identifying key systemic factors. We used an abductive approach, combining bottom-up coding of the papers to highlight features of systems, elements that could be identified as systemic factors, as well as relevant themes (to link features and factors to specific contexts). We also used top-down codes, based on Van Mierlo et al. (2010), to guide the identification of system features and cluster the systemic factors.

4.2 Understanding systems in SFS literature on dynamics

The variety of terms such as food system, farming system, agri-food system, agricultural system, or socio-ecological system commonly used in agri-food research illustrate the importance of systemic approaches to these issues. Behind this common term, however, lie different conceptions of what a system is. Very few of the publications reviewed explicitly define the term. The result is a polysemy covering different understandings of “system”. By extrapolating from how certain publications introduce the elements characterizing what they mean by system, we identify three conceptions. The system as a network of social relations, the system as a connection of heterogeneous elements and the system as a structuring narrative. These understandings are not necessarily exclusive

Systems as social relations

Several authors apply the notion of system to depict and analyse primarily social interactions among humans. Spies et al. (2022) introduce the concept of a system as a framework for understanding social interactions within the biomass sector. The existence and nature of such relationships are what renders a project or an initiative possible. Lamine et al. (2019) explore the reconfiguration of power relations in agrifood systems and presents a conceptual framework inspired by transition studies and political science. They emphasize the need to understand the mechanisms underlying power relations within these systems. Polge & Pagès (2022) discuss the embeddedness of economic activity and the dynamics of information diffusion, innovation, and cohesion within agri-food systems by adopting a social capital lens. They highlight the importance of social ties in the diffusion of agro-ecological practices. The findings of this study highlight the importance of social network analysis when researching system dynamics.

Connecting heterogeneous elements

Another understanding of the notion of system that emerges from the review is that of a web of connection of heterogeneous elements. The nature of the interconnected multiplicity varies based on scale. These might be different types of organisations, different localities, and most often highlights the interconnectedness of human and non-human entities,

Dornelles et al. (2022) highlight the role of global food systems in connecting different aspects of well-being, sustainable consumption, and production, and life on land. It suggests that systems thinking is necessary to address the challenges and complexities of global food systems.

Several authors introduce the concept of a social-ecological system, which emphasizes the interdependence between social and ecological components. This framework recognizes that systems are influenced by various actors, including government, producers, consumers, and businesses, each with their own perspectives and values. In addition, they emphasize the interdependencies between social and ecological components and emphasize the need for integrated approaches to address sustainability issues (Dentoni et al., 2017). De Herde et al. (2022) mention the social-ecological system framework as a tool for understanding the dynamics and challenges of agrifood systems. This framework recognizes the interdependencies between social and ecological components and emphasizes the

need for integrated approaches to address sustainability issues. For Anderson & Leach (2019, p. 8). “Food systems are the epitome of socioecological systems and have always included both social and ecological/biophysical inputs and dynamics, yet analytical tools and concepts of socioecological systems that truly integrate social and ecological science perspectives are not yet mature”

System as a narrative

In addition, several authors highlight the discursive nature of systems that emerges when elements become interrelated through narratives. Such narratives can contribute to reframe systems (Anderson & Leach, 2019). This conception suggests that systems should be conceived as heuristics, open to diverse perspectives and narratives. This implies that a system is not a fixed entity but rather a dynamic construct influenced by different actors and their interests.

These narratives become a key factor in building the system, but also for understanding it. Darnhofer (2021) discusses the use of narratives in analysing the process of farm development. They highlight the importance of considering different narrative flows and perspectives to gain a deeper understanding of the farm's becoming. Polge & Pagès (2022) develop on the methodological implications of this conception. Their paper emphasizes the role of narratives in coding and processing data, allowing researchers to identify phases and patterns within the system. These papers demonstrate the recognition of narratives as an important aspect of understanding systems. By considering diverse narratives and perspectives, researchers can gain insights into the complexities and dynamics of systems.

4.3 Systemic factors in the SFS literature

Within these different understandings of the notion of system, one common element is that the nature of relationships between the elements can create positive or negative dynamics. As described in the introduction, systemic factors are factors that emerge from the relational nature of the system and enable or constrain single elements within the system. Although the terms used vary across papers, we use the terminology of drivers, barriers and lock-ins to introduce these systemic factors identified in the SFS literature.

4.3.1 Drivers towards SFS

We identify as drivers, a range of factors that contribute to the transformation towards sustainability within farming systems. From the reviewed papers we categorized following drivers

Institutional Innovation

Institutional innovation refers to the development and implementation of new rules, norms, and practices within the institutional framework governing the food system. It involves the creation of new institutions or the adaptation of existing ones to address sustainability challenges and promote positive change.

One such paper that discusses institutional innovation is Garrett et al. (2020). This paper explores the role of institutions and innovation systems in promoting change in agri-food systems. It emphasizes the importance of institutional innovation in driving the transition towards more sustainable and resilient food systems. The authors argue that institutional innovation can help address barriers and lock-ins that hinder the adoption of sustainable practices and technologies. Akimowicz et al. (2022) review the literature on innovation systems to design an institutionalist conceptual framework for assessing the governance of the French varietal innovation system. They discuss the articulation of private, collective, and public resources within the current institutional framework and highlight the need for institutional innovation to ensure the legitimacy and effectiveness of the governance system. Furthermore, Verburg et al. (2022) discuss the use of innovation system frameworks, including institutional innovation, to study the transition of agricultural systems towards sustainability. Their paper highlights the usefulness of these frameworks in understanding the barriers and drivers of sustainable agriculture and emphasizes the role of institutional innovation in overcoming institutional problems and promoting sustainable practices.

Technological Innovation

Technological innovation is also a factor that supports the transition towards a more sustainable food system within the literature. Linares et al. (2022) mention the role of technological innovation in enabling progress in the transition pathway. For example, the adoption of precision farming technologies, remote sensing, and data analytics can

optimize resource use, reduce environmental impacts, and lead to more sustainable farming systems. For Rohe et al., (2022), technological innovation drives the transition towards sustainable practices. Their paper highlights how certain technologies, such as photovoltaic modules and wind power, have diffused sufficiently, leading to a shift in attention towards other, more complex technological innovation systems in the sector and how such dynamics can be reproduced in the food system. Young et al. (2022) explore the potential of technological innovation in the wine industry. They mention the use of robots in vineyards, disease modelling, and weather stations as examples of technological advancements that can contribute to sustainable wine production. Although they primarily focus on social innovations, Pereira et al. (2020) underline the role of technological innovation in driving food system transformation in South Africa. The paper highlights various innovations, such as phone apps for linking small-scale fishers to consumers and organizations bridging indigenous knowledge holders with chefs and restaurants. These technological innovations contribute to improving market access, knowledge exchange, and collaboration within the food system. As such they also highlight the entangled nature of many drivers.

Social Innovation

Social innovation refers to the development and implementation of new ideas, practices, and models that address social challenges and promote positive change in society. In the context of agri-food systems, social innovation plays a crucial role in driving the transformation towards more sustainable and inclusive practices. Anderson & Leach, (2019) emphasize the importance of social innovation as a driver for positive change in the food system. They highlight how social innovation can lead to the integration of traditional and scientific knowledge. The paper also discusses the role of social innovation in addressing power dynamics and promoting more inclusive and equitable food systems. Indeed, social innovations in food systems can take various forms, such as social movements around access to land and agro-ecology, that are driving positive change in the food system (Pereira et al., 2020). These social innovations aim to address social inequalities, promote sustainable practices, and enhance collaboration among different actors in the food system. Lamine et al. (2019) discuss the role of social innovation in sustainability transitions in agriculture. The paper discusses various conceptual approaches that go beyond traditional macro and micro approaches and emphasize the importance of social innovation in driving change processes. It highlights the context-dependency of social innovation and the need to consider long-term case studies from different countries to understand its dynamics. Verburg et al. (2022) highlight the importance of social innovation in empowering farmers for innovation through communities of practice. By fostering knowledge exchange, collaboration, and learning among farmers, social innovation can support the adoption of sustainable practices and the transformation of agricultural systems.

Knowledge Exchange and Learning

The exchange of knowledge and learning from different stakeholders is a driver for the transition towards sustainability. Knowledge exchange and learning play a crucial role in promoting innovation, collaboration, and the adoption of sustainable practices within the food system. De Herde et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of stakeholder engagement and the particular challenges faced by organizations in processes of transition. By promoting knowledge sharing, capacity building, and learning networks, stakeholders can drive the adoption of innovative and sustainable agri-food practices. Akimowicz et al. (2022) explore the absorption of knowledge by social actors in the French varietal innovation system. The paper discusses how social actors process new information and learn, both from formal and tacit knowledge sources. It emphasizes the importance of knowledge exchange and learning in facilitating innovation and promoting sustainable practices within the agricultural sector. Additionally, Morrissey et al. (2014) mention the importance of knowledge exchange and learning in the context of stakeholder engagement. The paper discusses how stakeholder engagement processes can facilitate the co-production of knowledge and build stakeholders' competence. It highlights the role of knowledge exchange and learning in empowering stakeholders to make informed decisions and contribute to sustainable development.

Verburg et al. (2022) underline the importance of knowledge development and exchange. Their paper mentions how knowledge is continuously evolving, and innovations are being developed, such as new types of dairy cow breeds. The paper also mentions the role of specialized knowledge brokers in facilitating knowledge exchange. The paper related knowledge exchange to institutional and social innovation, highlighting its significance in driving transformation in the agri-food system.

Policy and Governance

Policy and governance mechanisms play a critical role in supporting the transition towards sustainability in the food system. Klerkx & Begemann (2020) highlight the role of policy processes in removing barriers to sustainable food systems in Europe. Policy frameworks that incentivize sustainable practices, provide financial support, and promote market opportunities for sustainable products can act as drivers for the transition. Linares et al. (2022) argue for the importance of policy factors, specifically the EU CAP 2014-2020, in shaping agroecological farming systems and transitions. Policy frameworks and regulations that promote sustainable practices, such as agroecology, organic farming, and biodiversity conservation, can act as drivers for the transformation of the food system.

Ada et al. (2022) underline the importance of government support towards public procurement in promoting sustainable practices. They argue for the role of policy and governance in creating an enabling environment for sustainable procurement practices and addressing barriers such as lack of government support. Morrissey et al. (2014), take the example of natural resources and the need for multi-pronged approaches. The paper highlights the role of policy integration and governance measures in addressing challenges related to production and consumption in the context of natural resource management. It emphasizes the importance of policy and governance in promoting sustainable resource use and addressing fragmented approaches. Furthermore Lamine et al. (2019) mention the politics of scale in urban agriculture governance and the role of policy and governance in shaping food policy councils and promoting food democracy. The paper highlights the importance of policy and governance in addressing issues of fairness, social justice, and guiding transition processes in urban agriculture. Additionally, Bergeret & Lavorel (2022) mention the need for cross-sectoral governance and integrated approaches to address environmental challenges. They discuss the role of policy and governance in coordinating and restructuring governance systems to achieve better articulation between rules and preserve/mobilize natural resources effectively. They emphasize the importance of policy and governance in avoiding conflicts and addressing sectoral limitations.

Markets and Consumer Preferences

Changing market demand and consumer preferences can also drive the transition towards a more sustainable food system. Besides governance, Klerkx and Begemann (2020) discuss the importance of market dynamics in shaping agri-food systems. Increasing consumer awareness and demand for sustainable and locally produced food can drive the adoption of sustainable practices by farmers and food producers. Furthermore, Kuokkanen et al. (2017) explore how agri-environmental policies can influence market demand and consumer preferences by creating an enabling environment for sustainable food production and consumption. It emphasizes the need for public policies that encourage sustainable practices along the entire food value chain, including farmers, consumers, and opinion leaders. Linares et al. (2022) also see the role of policy and governance when mentioning the importance of aligning policies with market demand and consumer preferences to drive the adoption of sustainable practices. They highlight the need for policies that provide incentives for farmers to meet consumer demands for sustainable and locally produced food.

4.3.2 Barriers towards SFS

Barriers are those systemic factors that hinder or pose challenges for the transformation towards SFS.

Economic Challenges

Gomes & Reidsma (2021) highlight the recurring theme of economic challenges faced by farmers. The lack of compensation for investing in environmental practices and the feeling of inequity in shouldering the costs while society receives the benefits act as barriers to the adoption of sustainable practices. Financial constraints and the need for monetary incentives to scale up sustainable practices pose challenges to the transformation towards sustainability.

Ada et al. (2021) discuss economic barriers within the context of circular economy implementation. They highlight the economic challenges associated with the cost of implementing green activities and the increasing production costs. These types of economic barriers can hinder the transition towards a circular economy in the agri-food sector. Rohe et al. (2022) mention economic challenges in the context of the business model for organically bred vegetable varieties. They highlight that the business model of most actors in the TIS (Transition Innovation System) is not economically viable in the dominant market environment. This lack of economic viability limits the financial resources available for companies and initiatives, hindering their ability to drive forward diffusion and attract public funding.

Knowledge Gaps

Several authors identify knowledge gaps or lack of knowledge as a barrier to SFS. In the context of systemic factors, knowledge gaps do not refer to lack of knowledge by individuals but rather to the lack of circulation of knowledge within the system. Verburg et al. (2022) mention barriers in knowledge development and exchange within the context of the Dutch organic dairy sector. While the interviewees did not indicate these functions to be problematic, the paper highlights the importance of specialized organic research from companies and a declining research budget as potential barriers. These knowledge gaps can limit the availability of information and hinder the adoption of sustainable practices.

Rohe et al. (2022) discuss knowledge-related barriers to the diffusion of organically bred vegetable varieties. It highlights the lack of awareness and understanding of the concept of organically bred vegetable varieties among relevant actors in the vegetable value chain. This knowledge gap can impede the diffusion and adoption of sustainable vegetable varieties.

Institutional Inertia

Institutional inertia refers to the resistance to change within existing institutional structures and practices, which can hinder the adoption of sustainable practices. Dumont et al. (2020) raise the question of challenges posed by institutional inertia. The existing institutional arrangements and practices may be resistant to change, making it difficult to transition towards more sustainable food systems. Overcoming institutional inertia and fostering institutional innovation are necessary to address this barrier. Engelberts et al. (2021) highlight the need for systemic analysis and regime change to overcome barriers in the dairy sector's sustainable market transformation. While the paper does not specifically mention institutional inertia, it emphasizes the importance of addressing fragmented policies and inadequate resources as challenges faced by farmers. These challenges can be indirectly related to institutional inertia, as existing institutional structures may impede the adoption of sustainable practices. De Lauwere et al. (2022) mention external barriers, including legislation, as obstacles to the transition towards Conservation Agriculture (CA). Existing legislation can reinforce institutional structures that may resist change and hinder the adoption of sustainable practices.

Market Dynamics

Young et al. (2022) discuss the social aspects that enable or hinder transformations towards more sustainable agriculture. The market dynamics and consumer preferences play a significant role in shaping the agri-food system. The lack of market demand for sustainable products and the dominance of conventional agriculture can act as barriers to the adoption of sustainable practices. Creating market incentives and consumer awareness about the benefits of sustainable agriculture are crucial for overcoming this barrier.

Verburg et al. (2022) highlight the barriers to the adoption of organic products and mentions the lack of consumer demand as a significant barrier. They discuss how consumer preferences, such as price sensitivity and willingness to pay, can influence the growth of organic products in the market. The paper also mentions the role of media articles in shaping consumer perceptions and preferences towards organic products. Ada et al. (2022) discuss the barriers and drivers of circular economy practices in the agri-food sector. Their paper mentions market formation as a significant barrier, and within that barrier, lack of demand is mentioned most often. It highlights the importance of market demand in driving the adoption of circular economy practices and emphasizes the need for consumer willingness to purchase sustainable products.

Complex Realities and Interactions

El Bilali (2019) emphasizes the complexity of managing transitions towards sustainability in the agri-food system. The interactions between ecological, economic, and social processes pose challenges to the transformation towards sustainability. The heterogeneity of farming systems due to various factors, including economic, political, social, ecological, and climatic, makes it challenging to implement uniform sustainable practices. Understanding and addressing these complex realities and interactions are essential for overcoming this barrier.

Because of the dynamic nature of the interactions within agri-food systems, lock-ins can emerge.

4.3.3 Lock-ins

A lock-in refers to a self-reinforcing mechanism that maintains the dominance of a certain technology, practice, or system over time, making it difficult to transition to more sustainable alternatives. While the term "lock-in" may not be explicitly mentioned in all the papers, they discuss related concepts and barriers that contribute to the understanding of lock-ins in the context of sustainability transitions.

System lock-ins

Kuokkanen et al. (2017) identify a "food system lock-in" that operates at the whole system level. This lock-in refers to the transformation of the food system into an irreversible self-feeding process that threatens planetary boundaries and food security. The paper explores the roots of this lock-in and its empirical grounding in the historical narrative of the food system transition in Finland. It highlights how the food system's lock-in state can undermine its own existence by deteriorating its capacity to cope with resource scarcity and environmental instability.

Anderson & Leach (2019) call for systemic approaches and the analysis of power in studying food system change. Their paper mentions the identification and analysis of various lock-ins that prevent societies from transforming food systems, despite the negative consequences to health, quality of life, and ecological integrity. The notion of "food regimes" used by Klerkx & Begemann (2020) also suggests that the dominant food system structures and practices can create lock-ins that prevent the transition to more sustainable and resilient food systems. Furthermore, Calo et al. (2021) discuss the logics of global North property regimes as a key lock-in that waters down food system reform ambitions.

Technology and practice lock-ins

This lock-in refers to the self-reinforcing mechanisms that support the dominance of a certain technology or practice over time. De Herde et al. (2022) describes Walloon dairy cooperatives and their evolution, highlighting how lock-ins can define the trajectory of these cooperatives and hinder their diversification towards higher added value products. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding path dependency and lock-in effects in the context of collective action and regulatory frameworks.

Sutherland et al. (2012) discuss technological lock-in in the context of intensive agriculture. Investment in machinery characteristic of intensive agriculture can create a lock-in situation. Farmers who have made significant investments in machinery may be reluctant to convert to organic farming due to the financial loss associated with selling their spraying equipment. This example indirectly suggests the presence of a technology lock-in that hinders the adoption of alternative practices.

Akimowicz et al. (2022) discuss the potential lock-in in the French varietal innovation system. While the paper primarily focuses on the governance of the innovation system, it indirectly addresses the potential lock-in in the adoption of specific technologies or practices. The study examines the articulation of private, collective, and public resources within the current French varietal innovation system, highlighting the need to assess the legitimacy of the governance and the potential for lock-ins to hinder adaptation to climate changes. Furthermore, Kuokkanen et al. (2017) mention the adoption of chemical fertilizers and its impact on production logic in the agri-food sector. The paper highlights how the adoption of chemical fertilizers created a push towards intensifying and specializing production, which created expectations of ever-increasing production. This example indirectly suggests the presence of a practice lock-in that reinforces the reliance on chemical fertilizers and hinders the adoption of alternative practices.

Knowledge and Cultural lock-ins

For Sutherland et al. (2012) farming knowledge, influenced by practical experience and formal training, can lead to lock-ins in farm decision-making. The choice of agricultural colleges and specific courses can shape farmers' approaches to farming and limit the consideration of alternative practices. This knowledge lock-in can hinder the adoption of sustainable farming practices. Additionally, Huttunen, (2021) discusses the socio-cultural context of farming and proposes ways to break related lock-ins through sustainability transition research. While the paper primarily focuses on socio-cultural lock-ins, it indirectly touches upon knowledge lock-ins. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the socio-cultural context of farming and the need to design policies and interventions that promote changes in farming practices. This understanding implies the presence of knowledge lock-ins that can

be addressed through targeted interventions. Furthermore, De Herde et al. (2022) highlight the importance of understanding the historical trajectories and cooperative dynamics in the context of lock-ins. While the paper primarily focuses on technology or practice lock-ins, it indirectly addresses cultural lock-ins. The study emphasizes the role of past habits, narratives, and legitimacies in shaping lock-ins and hindering transitions. These cultural factors can create self-reinforcing mechanisms that maintain the dominance of certain technologies or practices over time.

4.4 The MLP and its relevance for understanding systemic factors in food system transitions

The MLP is a widely used analytical framework to study agri-food systems transitions. Over one quarter of the literature reviewed on system dynamics and SFS (56 references), explicitly uses the MLP as an analytical tool or makes some reference to it. This includes one review article on uses of the MLP in food related research (El Bilali, 2019). Due to its versatility, widespread use, ENFASYS puts forward as a central analytical framework to identify systemic factors. While acknowledging its many strengths, the literature and consortium partners also identified many weaknesses. In order to address these, it is proposed to draw on other systemic frameworks and explore original conceptual innovations throughout the project to rework the MLP.

Figure 4: The Multilevel Perspective (adapted from Geels 2002, 2011)

4.4.1 The MLP: main concepts

The MLP finds its roots within Science and Technology Studies where it was developed as a way to understand technological change over longer periods. The approach was further refined and popularized by the work of Frank Geels (2002) and led to the emergence of the interdisciplinary field of “transitions studies” (El Bilali, 2019). It is a theoretical framework widely used to analyse sustainability transitions in socio-technical systems. At its core, the MLP describes the transition towards sustainability of different socio-technical systems by conceptualising them as a regime change induced by the scaling up of radical niche innovations (Geels, 2002, 2011).

The MLP recognizes that systems are composed of multiple interconnected levels, ranging from individual actors and practices to broader societal structures and institutions. By identifying these levels and their interactions, it seeks to understand how changes at one level can influence and be influenced by other levels within the system.

The MLP categorizes the different parts of a system into three key elements: regimes, niches, and landscapes. **Regimes** represent the dominant structures and established practices in a system. **Niches** are the spaces where emerging innovations and alternative practices are developed. **Landscapes** encompass the broader socio-technical and institutional context in which the system exists. This framework allows researchers to analyse how changes in niches may eventually lead to transitions in regimes, under the influence of the broader landscape.

The MLP challenges researchers to identify feedback loops and circular interactions between different levels of the system. This understanding is crucial for grasping system dynamics since it shows how changes in one part of the system can lead to reinforcing or balancing feedback effects in other parts, thereby shaping the trajectory of the entire system.

By examining the relationships between the different levels and elements of a system, the MLP helps identify barriers and lock-ins that might hinder the adoption of new innovations or practices. It also reveals opportunities that could be leveraged to promote sustainable transitions or transformative changes in the system.

Overall, the MLP is widely considered to be a valuable tool for grasping system dynamics in complex socio-technical systems. It helps researchers and policymakers develop a more nuanced understanding of how different levels, elements, and feedback mechanisms interact, and how these interactions can shape the trajectory of the entire system over time.

4.4.2 Applications of MLP to study systemic factors in SFS transitions

Several aspects of the MLP appearing in the literature review on systems dynamics and sustainable agri-food systems hold particular relevance to the analysis of the transition toward sustainable farming systems. We found 17 papers that made extensive use or offered a detailed account of their application of the MLP. When applied to the context of sustainable farming systems (SFS), the MLP provides critical insights by helping to grasp social-technical change as an intricate interplay between various levels and elements.

Studies applying the MLP to Sustainable farming systems indeed identified a multitude of interconnected levels, ranging from individual farmers and their practices to broader societal structures, agricultural policies, and market dynamics. Depending on the study design (case study, review, interview-based research or system mapping), the studies focus on a different level and hence identify different scales where barriers occur. Some studies mention the importance of the individual (farmers) level by looking at perceptions, values or level of debt or knowledge (Engelberts et al., 2021; Magrini, BÉfort, et al., 2019; Vankeerberghen & Stassart, 2016; Vermunt et al., 2020). Magrini et al. (2019) mention change in values and individual abilities as “fundamental drivers” when it comes to enabling a sociotechnical transition towards SFS. A majority of the studies focus on factors at the regime level, such as constraining regulations, unclear policies, subsidies for unsustainable practices or high-yield targets (Bui et al., 2016; de Olde et al., 2017; Engelberts et al., 2021; Garrett et al., 2020; Kump & Fikar, 2021; Meynard et al., 2017; Morrissey et al., 2014; Wezel et al., 2020). The MLP's recognition of these diverse levels allows us to comprehend how changes at one level can influence and be influenced by other levels, unveiling the complex dynamics of the transition.

Most of the studies using the MLP are focusing on analysing regimes and niches. The prevailing conventional farming practices and institutional arrangements represent the dominant regime in the agriculture sector. By studying these regimes and contrasting them with emerging sustainable farming practices and innovations (niches), the MLP is taken as an approach that hints toward the potential for regime change and the challenges posed by incumbent practices.

Such studies often take the form of case studies focusing on a given value chain, a supply chain, or an area (Bui, 2021; Engelberts et al., 2021; Garrett et al., 2020; Hermans et al., 2016; Nemes & Augustyn, 2017; Rossi et al., 2019; Salavisa & Ferreiro, 2018; Vermunt et al., 2020).

Another strength of the framework is to enable researchers to look at systemic factors enabling or hindering the transition at various levels and analysing their effects at each level. Bui (2021) who examined niche-regime interaction in an agroecological transition in France found that lock-ins have a scalar dimension and can be overcome by changing the scale of an intervention, for instance by addressing local representatives of an organisation, instead of national ones. Vermunt et al. (2020) underlines that this scalar dimension is especially relevant for the transition of agri-food systems as the agricultural sector is strongly geographically embedded.

4.4.3 Reworking the MLP as an analytical framework

ENFASYS acknowledges that the MLP has been criticized from diverse scholarly perspectives (Geels, 2011, 2019; Shove & Walker, 2010; Smith et al., 2010; Sorrell, 2018; Sovacool & Hess, 2017; Svensson & Nikoleris, 2018; Wells & Lin, 2015). Elements of that were also touched upon in discussions within the ENFASYS consortium include the MLP's alleged bias towards niche innovation, problematic conception of regimes as monolithic blocs, lacking consideration of micro-level agency, mystification of macro-social tendencies, lacking materialism and explanatory power, etc. It is suggested that through reflexive application and rethinking of core concepts (Sorrell, 2018), grassroots conceptual innovation (Geels, 2019) and use of auxiliary theories (Geels, 2011; Markard & Truffer, 2008; Mattioni et al., 2022) the MLP can be reworked based on theoretical and empirical work during the project. Even so, as the previous section illustrates, researchers and stakeholders gain a comprehensive framework to assess the challenges and opportunities involved in transitions toward sustainable food systems. It offers valuable insights into the interactions between actors, practices, institutions, policies, and market forces, contributing to the development of effective strategies and policies to foster the much-needed sustainability shift in agriculture.

5 Behavioral factors and SFS

ENFASYS aims at identifying a comprehensive set of behavioural factors related to farmer, consumer, and other food chain actor decision-making towards different intervention options across case studies and at EU-level. The behavioural perspective focuses on the individual and investigates the behavioural or psychological factors (i.e. the cognitive, emotional, personal, and social processes or stimuli) underlying human behaviour. A behavioural perspective is therefore interested in what drives individual decision making, and is therefore not looking to systemic barriers and levers (governance, value chain dynamics, social media, technological change), even though these might be registered at an individual level as a factor (e.g. perceptions about economic feasibility, insufficient training, socially inappropriate, not in line with personal values, etc.).

5.1 Behavioural theories

Within the field of behavioural science, there are different theories of human behaviour which aim to identify constructs which shape human behaviour; explain behavioural patterns; predict causal pathways of behaviour, including mechanisms and moderators of action; and ultimately shed light on when, why and how behaviour change does or does not occur (Michie et al., 2011, p. 502). Behaviour change theories help us identify behavioural factors and target them in interventions. They mainly stem from the disciplines psychology and economics/business/management/finance, but also from sociology/political science, mathematics/physics, biology (Kwon & Silva, 2020). Kwon & Silva (2020) reviewed these theories and identified 17 factors that affect the intention or motivation for behaviour (Figure 5): “The theories from psychology tend to focus on more subjective and personal factors like attitude, subjective norm, psychological distance, fear appeal, beliefs and values, reasons, interest and satisfaction, probabilities, risk and heuristics, and conflicting interests [...] while theories from sociology tend to focus on social interaction [...]]. On the other hand, the theories from economics, business, management, and finance tend to focus on slightly more objective and nonpersonal factors like different interests, institutions, rationality and utility, imagined scenario, responsibility, and external environment [...].” (Kwon & Silva, 2020, pp. 166–167). Many of the behavioural theories are criticised because they only examine the intention of a person to behave in a certain way and this intention only corresponds to the actual behaviour to a very limited extent. Meta-studies have shown that only approximately 25% of behavioural intentions lead to the corresponding behaviour (Sheeran, 2002). There is referred to as the intention-behaviour gap.

One approach that recognizes the intention-behaviour gap is the comprehensive action determination model (CAD model) developed by Klöckner and Blöbaum (2010). It claims that the influence of social or personal norms on behaviour is not direct but rather mediated by intentional and habitual processes. Moreover, it considers situational influences such as objective and subjective constraints. Habits were found to play a crucial role in the moderation of the relationship between intention and behaviour. This model combines the theory of planned behaviour, the ipsative theory of behaviour, the norm activation model, as well as the theoretical concept of habit.

Figure 5: Map of theories of general human behaviour (Kwon and Silva, 2020)

Figure 6: General sketch of the comprehensive action determination model. (Klößner and Blöbaum, 2010)

In the subsequent section, we present the results from a literature review on behavioural factors influencing the transformation of food systems before elaborating on how behaviour is conceptualized in the ENFASYS project.

5.2 Literature Review

In this chapter, we summarize the key insights that behavioural research has gained in recent years in the area of food and farming system transformation. We conducted two reviews of scientific literature distinguishing two groups of actors, farmers and consumers. We identified the relevant publications by searching the databases Web of Science Core Collections and Scopus for publication issued between 2000 and 2022³, leading to a result of 904 papers from Web of Science and 659 papers from Scopus. In a second step, we screened the abstracts of these publications and reduced them based on the following criteria:

- Focus on individual behaviour;
- Behaviour is considered in connection with drivers for behaviour or a synonym such as enablers, factor, lever, push, trigger, motivation;
- Consideration of decision-making processes concerning sustainable farming practices (providing food, public goods, but also sustainable energy, animal welfare), AND/OR purchasing practices and changed consumer behaviour (buying sustainable food products, buying labelled products (labels for sustainable food production, may incl. animal welfare), buying products from short supply chain (incl. farmers markets), reduction of food waste, reduction of consumption of animal products);
- Focus on case studies in Europe

Every paper was screened by at least 3 people from different organisations. Conflicts were resolved by majority decisions. This led us to the final number of relevant publications of 183. The papers were reviewed in a mixed deductive and inductive approach. We used the comprehensive action determination model (CAD model) developed by Klößner and Blöbaum (2010) as an overarching structure guiding the first level of categories. During the review process, we developed additional categories such as “emotions” which are only covered indirectly in the CAD model. The subcategories were developed inductively based on the material. Below we present the findings from the review according to the two groups of actors, farmers and consumers, on the other.

³ The search string we used was: (sustainab* OR agroecolog* OR organic* OR ("biodiversity friendly" OR biodivers*) OR resilien* OR regenerat* OR holistic*) AND (agriculture* OR farm* OR food) AND ((farmer* OR agriculturalist* OR breeder* OR peasant* OR cultivator*) OR (consumer* OR customer* OR "end user*" OR buyer*)) AND (behavio* OR motivation* OR attitud* OR conduct OR comportment) AND (adopt* OR chang* OR regulat* OR incentiv* OR lever* OR nudg* OR driver* OR influenc* OR pric* OR cost* OR intention* OR moral* OR norm* OR trust* OR value* OR risk* OR self-efficien* OR identit*) AND (transition* OR transformation* OR pathway* OR trajector*)

5.2.1 Farmer behaviour

Normative Processes

All farmers have their own version of what it means to be a good farmer (Cusworth & Dodsworth, 2021). An important question for farmers is whether sustainable farming is perceived to be socially accepted as a good way of farming (Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022; Murphy et al., 2022). Traditions in agriculture play a central role in defining behaviour, with dominating conservative traditions of land ownership, inheritance structures, and knowledge transfer (Bouttes et al., 2019; Burton, 2014; Busse et al., 2021; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Konzett & Grüner, 2022; Kováč et al., 2022; Murphy et al., 2022). There are voices that see environmental policies as a threat to agricultural traditions. This is an example of an anxiety-based value of identity (Murphy et al., 2022; Puupponen et al., 2022).

Productivism is the dominant social norm in agriculture and involves a commitment to intensive and industrialised agriculture, with government support primarily oriented towards production and increased productivity (Kaiser and Burger, 2022; Cusworth & Dodsworth, 2021; Busse et al., 2021). However, there are large differences between farmers and there are also shifts in values away from the productivity paradigm (Barnes et al., 2022; Bouttes et al., 2019; Burton, 2014; Lutz et al., 2017; McDonald et al., 2014).

Intentional Processes

Decisions on sustainable agricultural practices are mostly made on the basis of the benefits and importance of the environment for human activity. In this context, the conservation of agricultural and natural resources for future generations and the creation of a more socially just and economically viable food system through sustainability transformation also play an important role (Bouttes et al., 2019; Busse et al., 2021; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Drottberger et al., 2021; Hazard et al., 2022; Helfenstein et al., 2020; Hvitsand, 2016, 2016; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Kings & Ilbery, 2010; Knezevic Hocevar, 2019; Lutz et al., 2017; Matysik-Pejas et al., 2017; Möllers et al., 2022; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Sutherland, 2011; Sutherland et al., 2016). But there are also behaviours associated with sustainable farming practices that are chosen for their intrinsic value and that are altruistically motivated such as efforts for animal welfare and protection, farmers' desire to work outdoors, with nature and not against it, and being connected to nature (de Lauwere et al., 2022; Konzett & Grüner, 2022). Reconnecting with the land, the nature and the local community is seen as personally fulfilling, environmentally sustainable and more socially just and therefore motivates sustainable farming practices (Bartulovic & Kozorog, 2014; Bouttes et al., 2019; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Drottberger et al., 2021; Helfenstein et al., 2020; Hvitsand, 2016; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Kings & Ilbery, 2010; Knezevic Hocevar, 2019; Kováč et al., 2022; Lutz et al., 2017; Penvern et al., 2019; Schösler et al., 2013; Vaderna et al., 2022; Vercher, 2022; Winkler et al., 2019).

Risk assessment

Farmers are more willing to adopt sustainable practices if the risk is limited and benefits are expected. There are also people with low risk aversion that are willing to take greater risks and implement measures with high uncertainty (pioneers) (L. Bakker et al., 2021; Bjørnåvold et al., 2022; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Möhring & Finger, 2022; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Raimondo et al., 2021; Weituschat et al., 2022). Organic and agroecological farmers tend to be curious and they value space for creativity and challenge (Bouttes et al., 2019; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Konzett & Grüner, 2022). Younger farmers tend to be more open to sustainable transformation. They are more likely to see its necessity and are also better informed about and educated to adopt sustainable practices (Burton, 2014; García-Arias et al., 2015; Kováč et al., 2022; Matysik-Pejas et al., 2017; Sutherland et al., 2016; Zakova Kroupova & Malý, 2013; Zoll et al., 2021). However, age alone is an inconsistent predictor (Burton, 2014). Farmers who already adopt more sustainable production practices tend to be more resilient, less dependent, experience less uncertainty and have higher adaptive capacity (Bouttes et al., 2020; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Sutherland, 2011).

Situational Influences

The conventional food production system with its many pressures, standards, low participation and strong competition leads to low perceived behavioural control to change (Busse et al., 2021; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022; Kings & Ilbery, 2010; Knezevic Hocevar, 2019, p. 2; Piñeiro et al., 2020). Low product prices put competitive pressure on farmers, making their income precarious, increasing their workload, and depriving them of autonomy, participation, recognition, and distributional equity (Bjørnåvold et al., 2022; Bouttes et al., 2019; Busse et al., 2021; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022; Knezevic Hocevar, 2019; Murphy et al., 2022; Puupponen et al., 2022). Regardless of

how important other motivating factors are, a sustainable management practice must at least be economically viable for farmers to be willing to adopt it (Bartulovic & Kozorog, 2014; Busse et al., 2019; Cusworth & Dodsworth, 2021; de Lauwere et al., 2022; De Marinis et al., 2021; García-Arias et al., 2015; Ingrassia et al., 2022; Kings & Ilbery, 2010; Lioutas & Charatsari, 2018; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Puupponen et al., 2022; Sutherland, 2011; Sutherland et al., 2016; Zagata, 2010; Zakova Kroupova & Malý, 2013). Farmers are more likely to participate in sustainability activities if they have additional off-farm income, making them more financially independent (García-Arias et al., 2015; Sutherland et al., 2016; Unay-Gailhard & Bojnec, 2016). They participate in short value chains mainly to meet the demand for local and seasonal food (Drottberger et al., 2021; Guerrero et al., 2019; Hvitsand, 2016).

Farmers perceive to have the behavioural control to conduct sustainable practices if they feel competent (Drottberger et al., 2021; De Lauwere et al., 2022), if they have access to the necessary machinery, (De Marinis et al., 2021; Möhring und Finger, 2022; Piñeiro et al. 2020), if there are no technological lock-ins and path-dependencies (Bjørnåvold et al., 2022; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2020), and if suitable markets and value chain structures are in place (Bakker et al., 2021; Busse et al. 2021; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2020; Lutz et al., 2017; Matsysik-Pejas et al., 2017; Zagata, 2010). A switch to organic or other sustainable agriculture increases perceived behavioural control, both competence and autonomy (Bouttes et al., 2019; Hvitsand 2016; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Lutz et al., 2017).

Social interaction

A sense of community, social ties and inclusion can be leveraged for more sustainable farming strategies, they positively influence each other and provide meaningfulness, connected to collective (farmer) identity (Bakker et al., 2022; Bjørnåvold et al., 2022; Burton, 2014; Carson et al., 2016; Hvitsand, 2016; Lutz et al., 2017; Murphy et al., 2022; Vadera et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2018). There is more collaboration, mutual support and knowledge sharing between farmers and within the community in short supply chains (Carson et al., 2016, 2016; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Hvitsand, 2016; Lutz et al., 2017; Vadera et al., 2022). Especially in smaller and more direct farming systems, trust, engagement and communication between producers, consumers and other value chain actors are crucial for collaboration and success (Borsellino et al., 2020; Bouttes et al., 2019; Burton, 2014; Carson et al., 2016; Guerrero et al., 2019; Mastronardi et al., 2019; Vadera et al., 2022; Vercher, 2022).

Interest and satisfaction

Mistrust and disconnection in the conventional food value chain lead to pressure, frustration and lack of appreciation and recognition of sustainability efforts (Drottberger et al., 2021; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022; Hvitsand, 2016; Kings & Ilbery, 2010; Matsysik-Pejas et al., 2017; Murphy et al., 2022; Puupponen et al., 2022; Sutherland et al., 2013). There is a desire for more self-realisation, self-determination, autonomy or sovereignty vis-à-vis the prevailing, competitive food system. This is a motive for the transition to alternative farming methods and the questioning of power structures, despite possible loss of income (Bouttes et al., 2019; Cayre et al., 2018; Hvitsand, 2016; Vadera et al., 2022).

5.2.2 Consumer behaviour

Overall, there is a great heterogeneity of eating habits and constructs between different social groups. They differ in terms of norms on product quality, impact on health, taste, food culture and tradition (Davis & Papies, 2022; de Boer & Aiking, 2018; Elzerman et al., 2022; Eugenio-Gozalbo et al., 2022; Kaljonen et al., 2020; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017, p. 20; Tuscano et al., 2021). Younger people tend to attach more importance to sustainability and environmental concerns in their purchasing decisions (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022; Brunin et al., 2022; Chiripuci et al., 2022; Eckl, Marion et al., 2021; Kamenidou et al., 2020; Massari, 2021; Melovic et al., 2020; Petrescu et al., 2017; Stanciu et al., 2022; Zoll et al., 2021)

Normative processes

Food traditions and social norms play a central role in the selection of products and consumption decisions. For a food to be accepted, it needs to be culturally sensitive and appropriate (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Austgulen et al., 2018; Banovic et al., 2022; Clay et al., 2020; Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; de Boer & Aiking, 2018; Elzerman et al., 2022; Fernandes & Saraiva, 2022; Guerrero et al., 2019; Kaljonen et al., 2021; Krüger & Strüver, 2018; Mazzucchelli et al., 2021; Ogorevc et al., 2020; Onwezen, 2022; Paddock, 2017; Petrescu et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021). One example is the dominant culture of meat-eating and the associated masculinity status, which was found to be a form of social pressure (Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; Graça et al., 2020;

Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022; Lawo et al., 2020; Onwezen, 2022; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). Vegetarian and vegan diets are strongly associated with a minority identity and benefit from resonance within that group (Davis & Papies, 2022; Lawo et al., 2020).

Norms informing environmental awareness and an environmentally friendly attitude play a central role in promoting sustainable consumption choices. High level of environmental awareness is also informed by personal norms where the environment is considered worth protecting for altruistic reasons. (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022; Banovic et al., 2022; Blanco-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Boer et al., 2016; Brunin et al., 2022; Graça et al., 2019; Haider et al., 2022; Hvitsand, 2016; Loera et al., 2022; Melovic et al., 2020; Möllers et al., 2022, p. 202; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022; Tuscano et al., 2021)

Intentional processes

Reasons for more sustainable consumption include preserving agricultural and natural resources for later generations, and creating a more socially just and economically viable food system (Civero et al., 2021; Ingrassia et al., 2022; Stanciu et al., 2022; Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022). Furthermore, animal welfare is a motivation to choose organic and plant-based products, though not always the biggest one, and often with a large attitude-behaviour gap (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Boer et al., 2016; Clay et al., 2020; Elzerman et al., 2022, p. 2; Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014; Hoogland et al., 2005; Melovic et al., 2020; Möllers et al., 2022; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021). Generally, there is a strong cognitive dissonance in meat consumption and consumers' values and emotions and actions (Boer et al., 2016; Hoogland et al., 2005; Onwezen, 2022; Profeta et al., 2021; Seubelt et al., 2022; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017).

Sustainable consumption can be motivated by a strong environmental self-identity (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022; Banovic et al., 2022; Davis & Papies, 2022; Fernandes & Saraiva, 2022). Perceived effectiveness, i.e. the belief that each purchase has a positive effect on the environment, is of central importance to consumers. Lack of trust in certifications and labels can be a barrier to sustainable purchasing. (Austgulen et al., 2018; Eugenio-Gozalbo et al., 2022; Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014; Hirsch & Terlau, 2015, p. 201; Kamenidou et al., 2020; Miftari et al., 2022; Möllers et al., 2022; Pfeiffer et al., 2017). Also, consumers' risk perception of new technologies or their correlation with environmental concerns needs to be considered (Naab et al., 2021; Saari et al., 2021).

The local origin of food is one of the most important factors for food choices. Often, local food is associated with qualities such as freshness, taste, health, naturalness, food safety or with local food tradition, cultural value and authenticity (Brunin et al., 2022; Hvitsand, 2016; Miftari et al., 2022; Möllers et al., 2022; Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021). The desire to support the local economy also motivates people to buy local food and even pay more for it (Boer et al., 2016; Melovic et al., 2020; Vadera et al., 2022). However, in terms of actual purchasing behaviour, the value of regionality is subordinated to price (Lehikoinen & Salonen, 2019).

There is the pursuit of healthy eating. Organic, plant-based, local or otherwise more sustainable food is perceived as healthier, safer, more nutritious. These aspects are key purchase incentives that often carry more weight than environmental reasons. (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Blanco-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Boer et al., 2016; Drejerska et al., 2021; Elzerman et al., 2022; Fernandes & Saraiva, 2022; Lehikoinen & Salonen, 2019, p. 201; Mastronardi et al., 2019; Melovic et al., 2020; Miftari et al., 2022; Möllers et al., 2022; Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022; Onwezen, 2022; Petrescu et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Stanciu et al., 2022; Tuscano et al., 2021). On the other hand, scepticism towards the nutritional value and the healthiness of plant-based meat alternatives and diets is a barrier to reducing meat consumption (Arnaudova et al., 2022; de Boer et al., 2017; Elzerman et al., 2022; Lonkila & Kaljonen, 2021).

Hedonistic aspects of food

Food choices are an expression of lifestyle and identity, they trigger emotions, memories and pleasure (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Austgulen et al., 2018; Banovic et al., 2022; Clay et al., 2020; Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; de Boer & Aiking, 2018; Elzerman et al., 2022; Fernandes & Saraiva, 2022; Guerrero et al., 2019; Kaljonen et al., 2020; Krüger & Strüver, 2018; Mazzucchelli et al., 2021; Ogorevc et al., 2020; Onwezen, 2022; Paddock, 2017; Petrescu et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). Hedonistic aspects of food, such as the taste, the feeling of reward, sensory pleasure of eating play a central role and can lead to the choice of certain foods. Organic, "natural" or local products are often considered tastier (Boer et al., 2016; Brunin et al., 2022; Eugenio-Gozalbo et al., 2022; Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014; Melovic et al., 2020; Möllers et al., 2022; Petrescu et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021).

Vegetable alternatives, on the other hand, are often perceived as less tasty and meat dishes are preferred because of their taste and expected enjoyment. The success of meat substitutes therefore depends strongly on their sensory appeal (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Banovic et al., 2022; Blanco-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Clay et al., 2020; Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; Elzerman et al., 2022; Graça et al., 2019; Lehtikoinen & Salonen, 2019; Lonkila & Kaljonen, 2021; Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag et al., 2022; Weinrich, 2019).

Habitual processes

Food choices are often determined by unconscious habits and routines that are difficult to change (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Austgulen et al., 2018; Banovic et al., 2022; Clay et al., 2020; Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; de Boer & Aiking, 2018; Elzerman et al., 2022; Kaljonen et al., 2020; Krüger & Strüver, 2018; Mazzucchelli et al., 2021; Onwezen, 2022; Petrescu et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). Convenience is often an important barrier to more sustainable food choices, for example in relation to the more difficult access or preparation of such products (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Haider et al., 2022; Hirsch & Terlau, 2015; Hvitsand, 2016; Mastronardi et al., 2019; Matysik-Pejas et al., 2017; Möllers et al., 2022; Petrescu et al., 2017; Pfeiffer et al., 2017; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Zagata, 2010). Lack of cooking skills lowers perceived behavioural control for dietary change (Graça et al., 2019, 2020; Guerrero et al., 2019; Lawo et al., 2020; Lonkila & Kaljonen, 2021; Onwezen, 2022; Schösler et al., 2013; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017; Tuscano et al., 2021; Varela et al., 2022).

Research has also been conducted on the aversion to trying novel and unfamiliar foods such as plant-based meat alternatives, upcycled, or insect foods (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2022; Broeckhoven et al., 2021; Elzerman et al., 2022; Onwezen, 2022; Profeta et al., 2021; Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag et al., 2022). The curiosity to try new foods or different diets to motivate more sustainable food choices is generally rather weak (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Drejerska et al., 2021; Elzerman et al., 2022; Lonkila & Kaljonen, 2021; Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag et al., 2022; Varela et al., 2022). The consumption of meat is a habit that is considered normal and necessary, an essential part of a meal in many cultures (Arnaudova et al., 2022; Austgulen et al., 2018; Dagevos, 2021; Davis & Papies, 2022; de Boer et al., 2017; Elzerman et al., 2022; Graça et al., 2015, 2019; Hübel & Schaltegger, 2022, p. 2; Kaljonen et al., 2021, p. 20; Lawo et al., 2020; Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022; Onwezen, 2022; Profeta et al., 2021; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017; Varela et al., 2022).

The pandemic has influenced consumer habits, leading to panic buying as a response to fear and uncertainty and also to better food planning and waste prevention (Borsellino et al., 2020; Jafri et al., 2021; Massari, 2021; Stanciu et al., 2022). It has also led to increased concern about the environment, food safety and health value, and the need to buy local products has increased (Borsellino et al., 2020; Jafri et al., 2021; Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022; Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022). At the same time, the pandemic has had a negative impact on incomes and purchasing power, which has negatively affected sales of more expensive, sustainable options (Borsellino et al., 2020; Guerrero et al., 2019; Jafri et al., 2021) emphasize in this context that different meanings of dietary practices need to be considered when developing new products. A persuasive rhetoric can help change the meanings of dietary practices (Lawo et al., 2020).

Situational processes

Price remains one of the most important decision factors for food purchases. High prices are a key barrier to more sustainable food choices, especially for people with low incomes. People with higher incomes are more likely to choose organic and sustainable food (Bastounis et al., 2021; Blanco-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Borsellino et al., 2020; Brunin et al., 2022; Civero et al., 2021; Coucke et al., 2022; Haider et al., 2022, 2022; Hirsch & Terlau, 2015; Jafri et al., 2021; Kamenidou et al., 2020; Krüger & Strüver, 2018; Miftari et al., 2022; Möllers et al., 2022; Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022; Saari et al., 2021; Schäufele & Janssen, 2021; Seubelt et al., 2022; Stanciu et al., 2022; Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022).

5.3 Knowledge gaps

The focus of the literature review was on understanding behavioural factors promoting and/or hindering sustainable farming practices and sustainable consumption behaviour. The reviewed studies tend to focus mostly on understanding normative and intentional processes, as well as situational influences. These are very important domains to understand behaviour change. Habitual processes however, which are found to be crucial in order to overcome the important intention-behaviour gap has only been rarely studied in literature on farmer behaviour. This

is different for the consumption literature which puts quite some emphasis on understanding consumption habits, making an important contribution to shedding light on the citizen-consumer paradox or the dissonance of consumers' willingness to pay and their actual consumption behaviour.

Aspects that lead to higher satisfaction of individuals, such as autonomy and self-determination in the case of farmers or hedonistic aspects of food in the case of consumers are key to explain both habits and intentions. It is therefore important to integrate theories focusing on interest, satisfaction such as the self-determinations theory but also theories focusing on hedonistic aspects.

Understanding how farmers assess risks in relation to sustainable farming practices and how consumers assess risk in relation to sustainable consumption is key in order to understand attitudes in relation to behaviour change. Theories specialising on understanding risk assessment need to be considered.

The role of social interactions and belonging to social groups in determining norms and attitudes is often not directly addressed in behavioural studies. This is where sociological or political science lenses with their systems view such as the social network analysis can contribute.

In the ENFASYS project, we aim at designing interventions for behaviour change. Dessart et al. (2019) reviewed the findings from the previous 20 years on behavioural factors influencing farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable farming practices. They found that interventions aiming at promoting more sustainable practices among farmers are ineffective and insufficiently building on behavioural factors identified in scientific literature. Also, the broader behaviour change and implementation research literature claims that interventions for behaviour change are seldom drawn on theories of behaviour change (Cane et al., 2012). Where this is the case, however, only one single theory or selected constructs from a theory are applied (Davies et al., 2010). A review conducted in the domain of farmers' behaviour in the context of cattle diseases proved that the majority of studies lack a theoretical framework in their study design (Biesheuvel et al., 2021). Those that do apply a framework mostly work with the theory of planned behaviour which is criticized to insufficiently explaining the intention-behaviour gap. In this regard, Biesheuvel et al. (2021) also found that studies mainly focus on measuring intention rather than actual behaviour. Different studies emphasize that there is a risk of missing relevant theoretical constructs or including irrelevant ones where theory selection is not informed by a comprehensive theoretical assessment of the implementation or other behavioural problem (Biesheuvel et al., 2021; Cane et al., 2012; Carroll et al., 2023). Identifying the specific process underlying behaviour change might also be hindered by the application of several theories with overlapping theoretical constructs (Cane et al., 2012, p. 2).

5.4 Conceptualizing behaviour in ENFASYS

In the ENFASYS project, we conceptualize behaviour and interventions for behaviour change with the help of the behaviour change wheel developed by (Michie et al., 2011). This tool aims at approaching the understanding of behaviours in a systematic and theory-based manner, drawing on 19 different behaviour change frameworks from different disciplines studying behaviour. The COM-B model is a behavioural model used within the Behaviour Change Wheel to identify the best-suited interventions for targeted, significant, sustained behavioural change. The COM-B Model captures a wide range of factors influencing behaviour. In this model, 'capability', 'opportunity', and 'motivation' interact to generate behaviour.

- *Capability* is defined as the individual's psychological and physical capacity to engage in the behaviour concerned.
- *Motivation* is defined as all those brain processes that energize and direct behaviour. It includes reflective motivation, such as conscious decision-making (weighing up all the facts in a

Source: Michie et al (2011) The Behaviour Change Wheel: a new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions. *Implementation Science*

Figure 7: The COM-B Model (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011)

situation in a thought-out manner), as well as automatic motivation, such as habits or immediate emotional responses.

- *Opportunity* is defined as all the factors that lie outside the individual that make the behaviour possible or prompt it (e.g. physical and environmental infrastructure; social relationships).

Cane et al. (2012) mapped the COM-B model against the constructs identified by the Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF). The TDF sheds light into the different theories aiming at understanding influences on behaviour (Michie et al., 2005). It was developed by a collaboration of behavioural scientists and implementation researchers who identified 33 theories relevant to implementation and grouped constructs from these theories into domains. The collaboration aimed to provide a comprehensive, theory-informed approach to identify determinants of behaviour. Cane et al. (2012) found that the use of the COM-B model may help in identifying which constructs of behavioural factors are likely to be important in changing behaviour (Cane et al., 2012, p. 14). Starting from there, “intervention designers can be selective about the domains they investigate to inform the nature of the intervention” (Cane et al., 2012, p. 15).

The TDF framework helps us in relating the important behavioural factors identified in literature to the components of the COM-B model (Atkins et al., 2017). This is also the case for important behavioural factors that have only been insufficiently addressed by previous food system transformation literature: Habitual processes are associated to behavioural regulation and therefore the individuals’ psychological capability. Autonomy and self-determination in decision-making is related to the social/professional role and identity and therefore impacts on the individuals’ motivation. Risk assessment is connected to the beliefs about the behaviour’s consequences and therefore the individual’s reflective motivation. Social interaction is attributed to social influences and therefore the individuals’ social opportunity.

Whereas other aforementioned theoretical models are in some case more useful for undertaking a quantitative analysis to predict behaviour and outline specific causal pathways, the value of the COM-B model and the BCW is its evidence-based practical guide and basis for understanding behaviour in context and selecting and designing theory-based and appropriate behaviour change interventions (Carroll & Groarke, 2019).

The BCW is a practical guide which uses the COM-B model to systematically gain a deeper understanding of the target behaviour, identify what specifically needs to change (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation) and intervention functions (e.g., education, persuasion, modelling, environmental restructuring) that are most likely to result in meaningful, sustained change. Following the practical, stepwise guide of the BCW prompts practitioners to specifically consider, label and understand the target behaviours they are attempting to change; this is an important first step prior to the selection and implementation of behaviour change interventions which are then specifically targeted at those specific behaviours, and influential behavioural factors. With respect to identifying appropriate intervention options, a valuable contribution of the BCW is the categorisation of different intervention functions, which acknowledges the diversity of influence of different forms of interventions. The BCW identifies 9 *intervention types* and 7 *policy options*, listed below. Intervention functions are “the broad categories of means by which an intervention can change behaviour” (Michie et al., 2011). Policy categories are the “actions that can be taken by responsible authorities, such as a government body or assurance scheme provider, that enable the implementation of the intervention and support behaviour change” (Carroll & Groarke, 2019).

The primary stated goal of the BCW is to support behaviour change agents to design theory-based interventions and to increase the replicability and efficacy of behaviour change interventions. A primary advantage of the BCW is that while it is built out of a strong base of psychological theory and evidence, its simple and clear framework for understanding behaviour and selecting targeted interventions make it particularly useful when working within multi-disciplinary teams (Carroll & Groarke, 2019). For this reason, and for its central focus on intervention selection and implementation, its application is valuable within the ENFASYS project.

COM-B component		TDF Domain
Capability	Psychological	Knowledge
		Skills
	Physical	Memory, Attention and Decision Processes
		Behavioural Regulation
Opportunity	Social	Social Influences
	Physical	Environmental Context and Resources
Motivation	Reflective	Social/Professional Role & Identity
		Beliefs about Capabilities
		Optimism
		Beliefs about Consequences
		Intentions
	Automatic	Goals
		Social/Professional Role & Identity
		Optimism
		Reinforcement
		Emotion

Figure 8: Mapping of the COM-B model to the TDF domains (Cane et al. 2012)

Table 1: Intervention types and policy categories according to the BCW (Michie et al. 2014)

Behaviour Change Wheel Intervention Types	
Education	Increasing knowledge or understanding
Persuasion	Using communication to induce positive or negative feelings or stimulate action
Incentivisation	Creating an expectation of reward
Coercion	Creating an expectation of punishment or cost
Training	Imparting skills
Restrictions	Using rules to reduce the opportunity to engage in the target behaviour (or to increase the target behaviour by reducing the opportunity to engage in competing behaviours)
Environmental restructuring	Changing the physical or social context
Modelling	Providing an example for people to aspire to or imitate
Enablement	Increasing means/reducing barriers to increase capability (beyond education and training) or opportunity (beyond environmental restructuring)
Behaviour Change Wheel Policy Categories	
Communication/marketing	Using print, electronic, telephonic or broadcast media
Guidelines	Creating documents that recommend or mandate practice. This includes all changes to service provision
Fiscal measures	Using the tax system to reduce or increase the financial cost
Regulation	Establishing rules or principles of behaviour or practice
Legislation	Making or changing laws
Environmental / social	Designing and/or controlling the physical or social environment
Service provision	Delivering a service

6 Inter- and transdisciplinary integration in ENFASYS

In this chapter, we introduce how the CF supports interdisciplinary integration in ENFASYS. In a first section, we introduce how we will use the MLP to integrate between different traditions of social science research regarding what produces change in society. In a second section, we present the three types of knowledge approach, which enables to integrate knowledge from research

6.1 Linking systemic and behavioural factors

In ENFASYS, we consider agri-food systems to be composed by two fundamental types of factors that drive farmer decision-making in relation to sustainable farming systems: systemic and behavioural factors. The latter are centred around individual decision-making based on human behaviour, whereas the former deal with underlying structures. Inspiration can be drawn from Karen O'Brien's "three spheres of transformation" – the practical, political, and personal sphere – as a heuristic to capture all dimensions inherent in sustainability transformations (2018). The practical sphere comprises specific practices and behaviours, the political sphere "represents the systems and structures that facilitate or constrain practical responses" (O'Brien, 2018, p. 156), and the personal sphere deals with the beliefs and values that are used to construct the two former spheres. While interventions in the practical sphere can be easily measured and evaluated, they are impeded by the political and personal sphere (O'Brien, 2018). Thus, it is essential for ENFASYS to study and shape behavioural and systemic dimensions to understand current and changing behaviour. So far, however, research on SFS has fallen short of truly integrating these perspectives. It is ENFASYS' ambition to show, in research practice, that a rigorous and extensive behavioural science approach can complement and is complemented by the deeper but often local explanations provided by food systems research. Based on this research experience the project also has the ambition to promote collaborations of these often separated research communities.

Whereas it is the ENFASYS methodological framework's task to show how these interdisciplinary ambitions can be realized in research and innovation practice, in particular through the systems and behavioural based theories of change, the conceptual framework takes up the task of exploring how behavioural and systemic perspectives can be conceptually linked. In this section we suggest just a few of the potential inroads that will be explored during the project.

Section 5 shows that relevant strides have been made by different disciplines (economics, social psychology) to integrate insights on individual decision-making leading to the constitution of behavioural economics. Similarly, as section 4 shows, insights on the systemic factors of the food systems (systems ecology, rural sociology, institutional economics, etc.) constituted the broad fields of farming systems and food systems research. Now, when considering that both behavioural science and food systems research have sought to describe and explain actor's behaviours, and as such are concerned with the same phenomenon, it makes sense to consider how the conceptual apparatus of both these perspectives can be linked. Behavioural economic science seeks to explain decision-making in terms of actors' behavioural and situational factors, whereas food systems research understands these factors as a product of the systemic structures defining actor's social and cultural environment. As such behavioural and systemic perspectives are rather complementary as the causes identified by the former perspective (behavioural factors) are the effects explained by the latter perspective (social mechanisms and agency).

In section 4.4 we have presented the MLP as an analytical framework to understand systemic factors driving or limiting the uptake of sustainable farming practices by farmers. As a systemic perspective the MLP does not explicitly address behavioural factors. A few authors (Geels, 2020; Huttunen, 2021; Huttunen et al., 2021b; Morrissey et al., 2014) have suggested, however, that the MLP's attention to agency of individuals, particularly as it relates to the development of new rules, behaviours and instituted practices at the niche level, can provide an promising entry point, from which one can start analysing behaviour as constituting and constituted by any other of the analytical levels (niche innovation, regime elements, landscape pressures). To account for micro-level agency in transition studies, while still mobilizing the MLP to keep track of social-technical change occurring at multiple levels, food system researchers have increasingly been drawn, to social practice theory (Sovacool & Hess, 2017). Social practice theory aims at explaining 'why people do what they do', by noting that behaviours are driven by beliefs, values, lifestyles and tastes that express personal choice, which is very near to a behavioural science approach. Social practice theory remains a systemic approach, however, by suggesting that this human action is constrained or enabled by social systems, but also that human action and social structure are mutually co-constructed.

Figure 9: Social structure and agency according to the transformational model of critical realism (Danermark et al., 2019, p. 80)

Likewise, behavioural scientists (Lane & Rouwette, 2023) have come to terms with the idea that behaviour is not a series of isolated linear decision timeframes, but that individuals have to reckon with the outcomes, intended or not, of past decisions and also tend to take into account these outcomes in future decisions. We find then that more recursive, dynamic models of decision-making are also being put forward in the behavioural sciences as well (Figure 9).

Figure 10: Framework illustrating the location and role of behavioural effects relevant to system dynamics (Lane & Rouwette, 2023)

We find evidence then of a potential rapprochement of both disciplines, and the question is then raised whether we can establish one-to-one can find relationships between core categories of behavioural science (social norms, habits, personal beliefs/values, dispositional factors, capacity, motivations, opportunity) and core categories of food systems research (systems, social relations, social position/habitus, cultural norms, institutions, interests, power and agency) can be drawn. Further theoretical work must show if certain concept can serve as bridges between the disciplines, or whether the conceptual resemblance actual showcase markedly different perspectives on social behaviour rather than correspondence.

6.2 Three types of knowledge to align research goals and research output.

Data collection and empirical work conducted in ENFASYS serves different purposes. Work conducted in WP1, 2 and 3, will mainly focus in assessing the current situation regarding multiple SFS initiatives as well as understanding the role of behavioural and systemic factors in EU farming systems. WP4 will develop strategies based on theories of change, while WP 5, 6 and 7 will develop and text interventions and strategies to transition towards SFS. The different types of results generated within the project needs to be integrate to create impact.

The three types of knowledge approach (Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007) distinguishes the knowledge needed to generate change through a research project. These three types of knowledge are 1) **system knowledge** (or knowledge about “what is”, that is the current situation about an issue); 2) **target knowledge** (knowledge about how the system should look like in order to be sustainable); and, 3) **transformation knowledge** (knowledge on what needs to be done to get from the current to the desired situation).

Systems knowledge, as defined by this approach, focuses on understanding the genesis, current state, and trends of unsustainable situations in the food system. It involves analysing the underlying factors and complexities that contribute to unsustainable practices, such as resource depletion, environmental degradation, and social inequities. By applying systems knowledge, researchers can identify the root causes of unsustainability and develop a comprehensive understanding of the interconnectedness of various components within the food system (Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007). This knowledge can inform the design of interventions and policies that target the systemic issues and promote sustainable practices (Wuelser et al., 2012).

Target knowledge, on the other hand, is concerned with determining the need for change, setting goals, and identifying better practices within the food system. It involves assessing the current state of the food system and envisioning a desired future state that aligns with sustainability principles. Target knowledge helps researchers and practitioners define the specific objectives and outcomes they aim to achieve in their research on the transition to a sustainable food system (Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007).

Transformation knowledge plays a critical role in research on the transition to a sustainable food system by exploring the means of acting that can bring about the desired changes. This form of knowledge encompasses technical, social, legal, cultural, and other possible approaches to transform existing practices and introduce sustainable alternatives. It involves identifying and evaluating different pathways, innovations, and interventions that can lead to sustainable food production, distribution, and consumption. Transformation knowledge helps researchers and practitioners navigate the complexities of implementing sustainable practices and overcome barriers to change (Hoffmann, 2016; Jacobi et al., 2022; Wuelser et al., 2012).

To effectively utilize these three types of knowledge in research on the transition to a sustainable food system, an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach is essential. Collaboration and knowledge co-creation among researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders from various disciplines and sectors is crucial. By bringing together diverse perspectives and expertise, researchers can integrate systems knowledge, target knowledge, and transformation knowledge to develop comprehensive and context-specific solutions.

Furthermore, we need to consider the interdependencies and relationships between these forms of knowledge. They suggest that each type of knowledge informs and influences the others, and neglecting any one of them can hinder the effectiveness of research and interventions. For example, a deep understanding of the current state of the food system (systems knowledge) is necessary to define meaningful goals and targets (target knowledge) and identify appropriate strategies for change (transformation knowledge). By recognizing and addressing these interdependencies, researchers can ensure that their research questions, methodologies, and interventions are comprehensive and well-informed (Schneider & Buser, 2018).

7 Public and Private intervention for SFS

7.1 Public Interventions

By public interventions we mean public policies addressing agricultural and food systems. Due to the complexity of food systems, both in terms of the multitude of implicated actor types, as well as food supply chain activities and broader activities societal domains and interrelations between these, public policies stem from various policy areas; especially agricultural policies, environmental policies, trade policies and market regulation, fiscal and social policies, food safety, as well as education, development, research and public health (De Schutter, 2019; EEA, 2023).

Examples of publicly funded agricultural and food policies connoted with potential sustainability impacts that have been researched relatively extensively are AES Agro-environmental schemes (Giomi et al., 2018); public food procurement (e.g. Schleiffer et al., 2022; and Parsons & David, 2022 for an overview of policy instruments related to public food procurement); public policies that foster local food production and sales (Reina-Usuga et al., 2022), organic farming support policies (e.g. Acs et al., 2005; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Łuczka, 2019; Pawłowska & Grochowska, 2021), policies such as labelling and other information tools targeting “consumer responsibility” (EEA, 2023).

With regard to sustainability and the transition towards more sustainable agricultural and food systems, an important lack in public policies is the missing integration between these areas. For example, while environmental concerns have traditionally been integrated into agricultural policy design in the CAP, the dominance of economic interests resulting from institutional power relations, together with budgetary and trade concerns, have often led to the watering down of environmental measures (Alons, 2017). In addition, conflicting interests within one policy area a common, an example being balancing of environmental gains from renewable energies against environmental costs of intensive production (Feindt, 2010). Other studies point toward potential conflicts between self-governed arrangements at national scale such as nature conservation programs for farmers and centralized ones, such as production intensification enhancing instruments of the CAP (Runhaar et al., 2017).

Concerning local level policy implementing bodies like administrations, coordination between administrations becomes even more relevant when policy strategies and designs are built on integrating several or all agricultural and food system relevant policy area. As coordination among administrations from one policy area is already known as often being defective, coordinating and collaborating with administrations from additional policy areas adds a constraining element for policy implementation and complicates coordinated action in an overall setting of “administrative times and processes [that] do not respond in a timely manner to social demand (Reina-Usuga et al., 2022, p. 13).

Another critical aspect of public interventions is the question of legitimacy of policy pathways towards sustainable agricultural and food systems. Even though negative environmental and social externalities of dominant agricultural and food systems have been researched extensively and have become more and more difficult to contest over the last two decades, the practical implications for policy development are far from being uncontested. Apart from the more obvious reason of colliding interests between and within the various stakeholder groups, a perhaps more concerning one for policy development from an ethical point of view is the different impacts policies have on different stakeholder groups, making an overall socially just transition even more complex. Besides the ethical considerations regarding potential unfairness and creation of “winners” and “losers”, the feeling of being at the mercy of continuously changing, “arbitrary” policies is especially strong among farmers and is de facto a barrier for adopting and adapting measures from political instruments. The perceived legitimacy of public policies for agricultural sustainability is therefore important to consider in policy development (e.g. de Boon et al., 2022). When different agricultural policy goals and regulations do not align and conflict each other (De Schutter, 2019; EEA, 2023) – at the expense of the targeted farmer population in (many) worst cases – legitimacy cannot be reached and impact negatively on motivation to adopt farming measures (e.g. Hansen et al., 2022; Kaiser & Burger, 2022; Runhaar et al., 2017). Legitimacy may also be enhanced by new ways of doing policy, especially in developing policies by including stakeholders in participatory ways to “holistic and dynamic approaches which can represent societal goals, values and their interactions more fully (Dwyer, 2021, p. 4)”. This relates to the right of people to design their own food systems in the food sovereignty debate as well as food sovereignty debates (De Schutter, 2017). It implies coordination and exchange between a diverse and considerable number of actor groups, starting at local and/or regional level (defined territory) to reflect their specific needs and realities, leading to policy design that is inclusive

in its objectives and processes, by leaving its rigid frame, include stakeholders across and beyond government, including those whose voices are typically marginalized (e.g. Brent, 2022; Kugelberg et al., 2021).

It should be noted that the need for participatory and reflexive policy design processes is tied to the much-discussed problematic of watering down participation approaches during practical implementation (e.g. Pretty et al., 2020). Food system transformation associations have been discussed to reach different levels of participation and the collaboration with public bodies is key to reach higher levels (e.g. Huttunen et al., 2022). A prerequisite – and ideally part of the policy design process itself – is the development of a common policy frame, that is a common and coherent way of understanding the policy problem (cf. Kaljonen et al., 2021), an understanding that is also put forward in a useful participatory design methodology for agroecological transitions by (Duru et al., 2015) *How to make sure that we have a “just” participation should be addressed in workshop design for WP6, including the question of researcher-other stakeholder relationship, as addressed for example here in the context of stages in transdisciplinary research projects; i.e. Preparation stage: problem identification and structuring; Project phase: joint generation of solution-orientated knowledge; Follow-up work: re-integration and application of the generated knowledge* (Delzeit et al., 2021, p. 2).

7.2 Collaborations between Public and Private sectors

In the global context of modern economies, many companies seek to lower production costs by locating their production in emerging economies that feature lax application of environmental and social regulations (Rajeev et al., 2017). As a result, damage to the environment and severe human rights violations, such as chemical spills (Cuervo-Cazurra, 2018), unsafe workplaces (Bair et al., 2020), and inhumane working conditions (Malik & Abdallah, 2019) are common. Long and complex international supply chains, which are characterized by fragmented governance operating in multiple jurisdictions, have become common in food systems. Governments in producer regions are restricted in their ability to impose sustainability legislation because importers can simply source from a producer with less sustainable practices and associated lower production costs.

Unprecedented access to information by the consuming public has created increased pressure for companies to take responsibility for social and environmental issues related to their value chains (Boström et al., 2015; Mota et al., 2015). In a functioning market, this pressure should drive companies to adopt sustainable behaviour based on the assumption that consumers will reward, either with price premiums or increased custom, the companies that adapt their practices to socially and environmentally sustainable production. However, Lingnau et al. (2019) point out that consumers' ethical demands tend to not be reflected in their purchasing decisions, which suggests that companies will not perceive that their interests are aligned with societal demands for sustainability.

The failure of consumers to force their ethical demands with their purchasing choices means that the responsibility for ensuring that supply chains are socially and environmentally sustainable lies largely with the governments of consumer countries. This responsibility is typically addressed with legislation for sustainable production, which is one of the few options available, and one with which governments are familiar. (Chandler, 2012, p. 66) points out that “the whole of corporate history shows unequivocally that protection of the interests of stakeholders other than the shareholder has come not from voluntary corporate initiative, but from external pressure followed by legislation”. Hendry & Vesilind (2005) appear to agree when they point out that the strongest motivations for corporations to engage in environmentally sustainable behaviour are compliance with regulations, followed by cutting costs. However, Cossart et al. (2017) noted that government efforts to force corporate social responsibility (CSR) are usually met with strong opposition from the business sector, as was evidenced by the vigorous industry campaign against the recent Swiss ‘Responsible Businesses Initiative’ that would have extended liability over international human rights abuses and environmental harm caused by major Swiss companies and the firms they control abroad (Neghaiwi, 2020).

The ability of governments in consumer countries to legislate for CSR is complicated by international supply chains spanning multiple jurisdictions. Governments of consumer countries are therefore faced with the challenge of responding to public demand for sustainability by attempting to change the behaviour of actors who they cannot influence with hard powers (Nye, 2005) such as legislation. This dilemma is further complicated by industrial production being commonly transferred to emerging economies in the Global South (Rajeev et al., 2017), where legal frameworks are often insufficiently enforced due to lack of resources or corruption (Salmivaara, 2018). A further reason for lack of enforcement is that mobile industries can relatively easily relocate to competing economies with more favorable, from their perspective, legislative environments, and take their supply of international revenue with

them (Chan & Yang, 2022). Thus, governments of consumer countries must find ways to apply their powers to promote sustainable value chains when most of the chain, and most of the issues, lie outside their jurisdiction, and when the enforcement of legal frameworks is perceived by those with the power to do so, to be against their own interests.

These realizations have led to proposals for smart mixes (Gunningham et al., 1998) of hard and soft powers (Nye, 2005), with the concept having been mainstreamed by its inclusion in the UN guiding principles on Business and Human Rights “as an intelligent mix of national and international, binding and voluntary measures” (Ruggie, J, 2011, p. 8). (Kinderman, 2016, p. 30) commented that ‘a Smart Mix implies that private governance and hard law regulation are complementary, or at the very least compatible. The suggestion seems to be that a Smart Mix combines the best of both worlds: the flexibility, dynamism, innovativeness, reflexivity, and adaptability of voluntary market-based solutions and the authoritative, scope, and binding force of legal regulation’. On the other hand, (Kinderman, 2016, p. 39) also questions the political viability of the concept by questioning whether business organizations will voluntarily participate in Smart Mixes, simply because they are needed, and notes that ‘existing scholarship tends to over-state the convergence of public and private actors’ interests’.

However, such convergence is precisely what Ruggie, (2011) suggests that governments in consumer countries must achieve if they are to influence the behaviour of supply chain actors in producer countries in which social and environmental regulations are insufficiently enforced. An example of a functioning Smart Mix of public and private interventions is organic labelling. Organic standards and labelling are a bottom-up initiative from the organic sector, with many private labels resulting from coordination between actors, who are at times territorialized (Triboulet et al., 2019). These private labels have been protected at EU level and country levels by official organic labels that have been established by regulation. However, such examples of public-private cooperation are rare so it is worth examining motivations for the business sector to engage in sustainable behaviour.

Chandler (2012, p. 66) points out that the market economy survives today because it is not a ‘free market,’ but one bounded by moral parameters enforced by law,” but interventions leading to participation in public-private partnerships cannot be direct command legislation. The logic of multistakeholder alignment has been challenged, with Kinderman (2016, p. 31) arguing that “business organizations want to keep private governance private and that in most cases, public authorities have to overcome business opposition” to establish arrangements in which businesses adopt sustainable supply practices. While businesses cannot be forced to cooperate, a solution might lie in indirect legislation to create conditions so that it is in the best interest of businesses to seek cooperation. Connolly et al. (2022), for example, advocate reorientation of policies that enable small food businesses to move beyond the concept profit-maximizing to rather focus on reinforcing the regional spaces within which small food businesses operate to promote diversity, resilience, and sustainability in the food system. Spacek et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of collaborative partnerships and inclusive societies in addressing challenges and promoting sustainable transformation by means of co-production of knowledge, transformative social innovation, and collaboration between various stakeholders for knowledge co-production and diffusion. Haller et al. (2022) suggest development of symbiosis networks in industry to encourage collaboration between business and government as a way of transitioning to resilient and resource-efficient food production systems.

A further potential approach is due diligence legislation that, “rather than imposing pre-ordained behavioural rules” (Bartley, 2014, p. 94) places the responsibility of ensuring the sustainability of the production practices in source countries on importers. Due diligence legislation essentially requires companies to “conduct an ongoing, proactive, and reactive checking process in their supply chain in order to identify and manage the risk of contributing, directly or indirectly, to social and/or environmental harm” (Partzsch & Vlaskamp, 2016, p. 946). This shifting of responsibility counteracts the ability of producers to simply source elsewhere because alternative suppliers will also be subject to the same scrutiny requirements as part of due diligence. However, the ‘due diligence’ approach is subject to some weaknesses and can imply a substantial investment if done seriously (Trebilcock, 2020), so companies may actively attempt to avoid their responsibilities: especially in complex supply chains in which traceability is difficult (Koch & Kinsbergen, 2018). A further weakness of approaches based on mandatory due diligence is that individual importers may lack the capacity to effectively control the sourcing of their materials. Despite these weaknesses, due diligence legislation is seen as a powerful measure for supply chain sustainability: especially when supported by laws coupled with effective home state sanctions, such as administrative fines, on the relevant lead firm (Home et al., 2021, p. 13). Governments of jurisdictions in which due diligence legislation exists could offer support for due diligence activities, which would reduce the investment required by companies and be a strong motivation for them to engage in public-private partnerships.

7.3 Private sector interventions

A further motivation for companies to align with societal goals and design business strategies or models that overcome lock-ins to allow creation of sustainable products is when there is a perceived competitive advantage in them doing so. For a company to perceive such an advantage that would motivate them to adopt a strategy, which can sometimes reflect a dramatic change in vision, is the availability of data. (Muñoz Torres et al., 2022) pointed out the need for sustainability assessment tools and their inclusion in available information for decision-makers. Pakseresht et al. (2023) similarly point out that a successful transition to sustainability in the food sector requires overcoming the challenges of today's complex food supply chains, such as information asymmetry and poor cooperation among stakeholders.

New forms of governance, such as voluntary standards, certification schemes, labels, codes of conduct, and procurement guidelines that complement and go beyond the traditional command and control regulation may provide such a competitive advantage and motivate businesses to innovate (Del Vecchio et al., 2021; Kinderman, 2016). Ervin et al. (2013) studied motivations for corporations to engage in voluntary environmental management by combining two frameworks: 1) the utility maximization approach, which centers on using market mechanisms to decrease cost and increase revenue; and 2) institutional theory, which considers how external pressure, such as market pressure and pressure from NGOs, direct a firm's environmental efforts. They concluded that these frameworks are complementary and that both affect a business' environmental practices (Ervin et al., 2013). (Del Vecchio et al., 2021) searched for enablers and barriers to finding such alignment, which include: 1) Reacting to changing consumer behaviour, or consumption patterns, to create new markets; and 2) Increasing efficiency, such as by adopting innovative business models that include strategies, such as agility with short supply chains, optimisation of processes with cooperative business models, or optimisation of production with circular business models. A further strategy that is open to businesses seeking to profit from societal demand for sustainability is greenwashing, which refers to the practice of making misleading or unsubstantiated claims about the environmental benefits of a product or company (Taufique et al., 2022).

7.3.1 Social Innovation to create new markets

Consumer behaviour has been addressed in section 5.2, which reveals the rather clear results that consumers demand sustainable food systems. Although consumers play a crucial role in driving sustainable transitions in agri-food systems through their demand for transparency, traceability, and information about agri-food products (Sepide Mehrabi et al., 2022; Taufique et al., 2022; Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022), the societal demand is not reflected in purchasing decisions (Lingnau et al., 2019), so cannot be expected to carry the weight of being the driver for such behaviour. However, Taufique et al. (2022), with their finding that half of 'green' claims on company websites lack evidence, conclude that companies must perceive a need to react to the societal demands for sustainability or they wouldn't continue to make unsubstantiated claims in their public contact information. Indeed, Mehrabi et al. (2022) suggest that farmers, faced with societal demand, may create new markets for their products if they shift to a focus on interactions within the entire value chain, from production to consumption.

One means of aligning business goals with sustainable behaviour is to adapt to a niche market and meet the needs of specific consumers who make choices, and sometimes pay price premiums (Pawlewicz, 2020), based on sustainability. Muñoz Torres et al. (2022) examined short supply chains as a business strategy to become more sustainable and conclude by discussing the importance of incorporating social aspects in sustainability frameworks. Social innovation processes can give rise to new organisational formulas among farmers and contribute to the coordination and efficiency of food supply in Alternative Food Networks, such as food cooperatives, food buying groups, farmers' markets, community supported agriculture, and urban agriculture (Vercher, 2022), and digital marketing solutions such as web stores that allow sustainability information to be communicated directly (Csordás et al., 2022). However, supplying the sustainability demands of new niche markets with price premiums opens the possibility of competitors taking the role of free-riders, by seeking the price premiums without fulfilling sustainability demands

7.3.2 Greenwashing

An alternative to revising practices in reaction to societal demand for sustainability is to engage in greenwashing, which refers to the practice of making misleading or unsubstantiated claims about the environmental benefits of a

product or company (Möllers et al., 2022). Taufique et al.'s (2022) finding that half of 'green' claims on websites lack evidence is evidence of "greenwashing", which suggests that business managers must see some advantage to making such claims. Möllers et al. (2022) wrote that labels such as "traditional" or "natural" are sometimes used on products in Romania to imply that they come from low-input production with a high naturalness value but pointed out that consumers knowledge is low so conclusions about naturalness are mostly trust-based, which creates a potential for greenwashing.

7.3.3 Increasing efficiency

One means that businesses can align sustainability with competitive advantage is to reflect on internal processes can also lead to institutional innovation with the aim of increasing efficiency (Del Vecchio et al., 2021) such as by optimising production processes or adopting improved technologies to minimize the use of resources and thereby reduce the environmental impact per unit of output. Connolly et al. (2022) found that some small-scale artisan food producers reject the idea of chasing efficiencies and rather prioritize "minding what you make" and "making peace with enough" instead of solely focusing on growth and expansion for the sake of profits. However, the industrial reality of the majority of businesses suggests that increasing efficiency is an attractive strategy for most businesses, and one that can have positive sustainability outcomes (Del Vecchio et al., 2021). Strategies to increase efficiency include shortening supply chains to enhance agility (Stanciu et al., 2022), creating circular business models (Vecchio et al., 2022), and reducing waste with cooperative business models (Haller et al., 2022).

7.3.4 Efficiency: Agility in optimising products with short supply chains

Stanciu et al. (2022) suggest that short supply chains can increase efficiency due to the agility that comes with producer/consumer relationships, which allows them to tailor their production to market needs, such as those identified by Möllers et al. (2022). Martens et al. (2022) advocate hybrid cooperation models within the urban rural nexus, which link producers and consumers, as a means of increasing efficiency by enabling response to consumer needs and the creation of new markets. Muñoz Torres et al. (2022) noted the importance for a company to understand and satisfy the needs of their customers and suggest that shortening supply chains might be a strategy to improve ecological outcomes while increasing efficiency. They did, however, warn that diverting attention away from how the product is managed at its origin and using proximity as a proxy for sustainability could hide social or environmental inefficiencies in relevant sustainability issues, which might cover possible mismanagement.

7.3.5 Efficiency: circular business models

Circular business models are gaining prominence in the business discourse where they are promoted as a means of enhancing production sustainability by increasing efficiency and reducing waste. Del Vecchio et al. (2021) identified values, technologies, governmental policies, corporate environmental culture, networking, financial attractiveness, recognition, branding awareness campaigns, exploitation of public programs, usage of production waste, and the discovery of the value of local resources as enablers of circular business model design in the agro-energy sector. Despite their increasing prominence, an information deficit hinders the implementation of such strategies by food systems managers. De Bernardi et al. (2022) noted that, while reviews on the circular economy are spreading rapidly, no reviews have comprehensively addressed the critical issues for the transition to circular food systems in the business, management, and organization domains. Del Vecchio et al. (2021) noted that limited progress has been made in understanding the enablers of managerial practices for adoption of circular economy principles in business models. (Bakker et al., 2022) suggest that more attention should be given to the implementation side of the design process of circular business models to support business managers, such as farmers, in transitions to sustainable practices. De Bernardi et al. (2022) searched for critical issues and gaps in research related to circular food systems and identified seven recurring themes, including consumer behaviour, multi-stakeholder coordination, business models, digital technologies, barriers, transition processes, and performance and measurement systems.

The effectiveness of adoption of circular business models is dependent on various features, such as cross-sectorial dependencies and intersections, institutions, and the larger community of stakeholders (Del Vecchio et al., 2021). Haller et al. (2022) suggest that the use of centralized digital platforms can promote the circular economy by facilitating information transfer, such as company details, environmental and social aspects, and consumer feedback, in business decisions. (Pakseresht et al., 2023) similarly explored the application of blockchain technology and its potential for accelerating the transitioning towards a circular economy in the agri-food sector by improving data utility and supply chain management efficacy; enhancing eco-efficiency; and improving data management in

certifying product provenance and tracking products. However, (Charatsari et al., 2022) warn that advisors and professionals can be reluctant to adopt, and especially to base business strategies, around new technologies, such as those that are proposed as being supportive to the circular economy.

A further organisational innovation to create a circular business model is for businesses to adopt cooperative business models to enhance the efficiency of resource use and to valorise or reduce waste. Haller et al. (2022) suggest that expanding industrial symbiosis practices, such as sharing assets or using waste flows and by-products from nearby businesses, has a significant potential to create added value from a region's resources while at the same time making the food system more sustainable and resilient.

8 Conclusions

The goal of the ENFASYS CF as stated in the introduction is to facilitate a holistic analysis of the different research activities. Building upon the concept presented above, the CF serves as a roadmap to coordinate the different work packages objectives, to ENFASYS goal to foster SFS.

The significance of the conceptual framework lies in its comprehensive understanding of the diverse factors that influence transitions to SFS. Building on four systematic literature reviews, we identify research challenges linked to the analysis of the role systemic and behavioural factors and to effects of public and private interventions in farming systems.

We propose the adoption of the Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) as an analytical framework to bridge the gap between behavioural and systemic factors, thus making valuable contributions to the journey towards SFS. The MLP's depiction of sustainability transitions as regime shifts via radical niche innovations lays the groundwork for analytically linking micro-level agency, meso-level dynamics, and macro-level interactions. The three types of knowledge approach serves as a reflective tool to ensure that our analytical work with create impact.

The CF recognizes the project's interdisciplinary nature. Since behavioural and systemic approaches have different starting points, it's crucial to establish common terms. The definitions provided help partners from different backgrounds understand and use these concepts effectively. It is important to note that although these shared definitions create common ground, they will not necessarily lead to complete agreement. Functionally, the CF operates as a unifying lens through which different research activities are examined. It sets parameters that maintain coherence across the project while offering flexibility for partners to contribute their expertise

In conclusion, the CF is a dynamic tool that anchors the research project. The CF, as presented above can accommodate diverse levels of analysis, multiple methods as well as different types of interventions. Its role is distinct from the methodological framework, which focuses on how to conduct the research, whereas the conceptual framework focuses on what to study within the ENFASYS project.

Finally, the CF as presented here is not just a blueprint; it is a living guide that we will adapt and complete as the project advances, keeping in mind the objective to facilitate a holistic understanding of how to transition towards SFS.

9 Glossary

Actors

“The notion of actors usually refers to organizations such as companies from along the value chain, research institutes, or political lobby groups, but also individuals who actively contribute to innovating and applying the product, such as pioneering entrepreneurs or dedicated end-users” (Hekkert and Negro 2009, in: Rohe et al. 2022, p. 84). “Actors coordinate and exchange ideas or resources within informal network structures or formal networking organizations” (Rohe and Chlebna 2022, in: Rohe et al. 2022, p. 84). For ENFASYS, the entry point of research is the farming system level with the farmer as key actor. Other key change actors for forming systems change are describe in Table 2.

Table 2: Key change actors for forming systems change.

Categories	Description and examples
private sector organizations, actors in the food-chain upstream	inputs providers: seeds, machinery and chemical input providers
transversal service providers	financial institutions: banks or other financial institutions, insurance & risk management services
farming and support to farming	farmers, farmworkers and farmers unions/organizations/associations and federations, farming/rural advisory services/consultants, veterinarians, farmers' cooperatives, new entrants, farming press, veterinarians
industry representatives	agri-food companies, food industry, agribusinesses (collectors, logistics, food processing industry), other stakeholders who have a direct interest in the profitability of the farming system
distribution and marketing	retailers
consumers, citizens and voters	local communities, consumer organisations, press reaching out to the public, youth organizations
research/scientific organizations and education	social, economic and natural sciences (agronomic research) agricultural education institutes behavioural economists, sociologists, business experts, policy researchers, communication experts, food-system researchers
public authorities, government institutions, policy makers	government agencies, authorities, EIP-Agri & EU level policy makers, governmental/public, national, regional and local representatives of public entities responsible of tenders' requirements for public food procurement, local authorities with good practices
civil society organizations, NGOs	climate and environmental NGOs, sustainable agri-food NGOs, food-ethical consumption NGOs

Agricultural Systems

“Agricultural systems are defined as social-ecological systems that comprise social and biotechnical components, and fulfil agricultural objectives (e.g. production of food and fibre, renewable natural resources management, contribution to the socio-economic viability of rural areas) but that have additional environmental, economic and social implications. This definition includes the interactions between agricultural systems and systems ‘external’ to them that act as drivers of change operating at multiple scales such as agricultural systems with different agricultural

objectives, the broader local and/or global environment, policies, institutions, markets and thus food systems” (Skrimizea et al., 2020, p. 264).

Agricultural systems are understood as “a set of interconnected elements ecological processes and resources, knowledge and technology processes and resources (including, extension services and agricultural research, input suppliers, but also farmer knowledge) market processes and resources (input and outputs markets and patterns of demand) and policies and regulations (Conti et al., 2021, p. 3).

Barrier

Barriers are concrete aspects that hinder the development or uptake of an innovation, at any location within the system. Barriers can be operational, economic, financial, technological, institutional, governmental or social (Ada et al., 2022). “Internal barriers include organizational, financial, operations and logistics, marketing, public relations and research and development barriers. External barriers cover governmental, legal, societal, market conditions, environmental and technological barriers” (Ada et al. 2022, p. 933). Barriers can be related to knowledge, market, investments and legitimacy (Rohe et al., 2022). Farmers need specific strategies to overcome a barrier.

As an example, barriers to crop diversification include the lack of adapted machinery, the irregularity of productivity of new crops, supplementary or more complex workload. Barriers to agroecological innovations are found at every stage of value chains as well as in the context in which food systems are embedded. Barriers encountered by farmers when implementing or wanting to enhance diversity on their farm can be related to “land tenure, markets, regulation and subsidies, knowledge production and sharing or a lack of democratic influence” (Aare et al., 2020, p. 393)

Behavioural factors

Behavioural factors refer to elements that relate to the capacity of actors, such as farmers, buyers, citizens, investors to conduct a certain behaviour. It encompasses the whole range of factors that are to be taken into account in order to understand these behaviours. These factors vary depending on the theoretical approach used. However, they generally encompass elements such as attitudes, perceptions, knowledge, habits, emotions, experience, norms and values.

Attitude, meanings and intention

Attitudes are any cognitive and affective beliefs about a behaviour. Attitudes towards a particular behaviour under consideration are shaped by beliefs about the consequences of the behaviour, known as behavioural beliefs, which are interpreted within the individual by subjective evaluations of these outcomes (Sok et al., 2021). Combined they lead to a positive or negative attitude towards the behaviour (Ajzen, 2020). Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) scholars differentiate between attitude and intention. The theory states that three core components, namely attitude, subjective norms (see Social norms and group belonging) and perceived behavioural control (consisting of competences and autonomy), together determine a person's behavioural intentions (Ajzen, 2020). Closely connected to subjective norms (or social norms) are the concepts of Identity and Personal norms and values. Meta-studies have shown that only approximately 25% of behavioural intentions lead to the corresponding behaviour (Sheeran, 2002). There is an important intention-behaviour gap, which is often also referred to as cognitive dissonance. In Practice Theory, attitudes are considered part of the individual's *habits*. Habits determine behaviour and are the sum of an individual's behaviours, experiences, beliefs, convictions and dispositions (Cusworth & Dodsworth, 2021). Comprehensive Action Determination Theory combines the two above models by saying that the influence of social or personal norms on behaviour is not direct, but rather mediated by intentional and habitual processes (Klößner & Blöbaum, 2010). Further behavioural factors are *trust, risk and uncertainty* assessment and *emotions*.

Social norms and group belonging

People tend to want to feel they belong to a group. Belonging to a group implies the adherence of social norms that this group represent. Perceived social norms are pressures to act in a certain way (Onwezen, 2022). They can be injunctive (what ought to be done) or descriptive (what most people do) (Bauer et al., 2022; Berger & Burkhalter, 2022; de Lauwere et al., 2022; Mingolla et al., 2019). Social norms are a mediator for attitudes. They form intention either directly or mediated through personal norms (Berger & Burkhalter, 2022). Also, recognition, representation and prestige are important factors influencing attitude that are closely interlinked with social norms. There is a close connection to *identity*, including the fear of losing cultural identity.

Identity

A person's identity consists of a set of meanings that are associated with and support the individual. These meanings serve as a standard or reference for the identity. Personal identities reflect the individual's self-perception of possessing certain characteristics and qualities. It can be an individual identity or a group identity.

Personal norms and values

Personal norms are a mediator for attitudes, and as such they indirectly predict behaviour. Personal norms could also be described as a sense of moral obligation. Personal norms are sometimes used synonymously with 'values'. Personal norms include aspects such as autonomous decision-making and self-determination, health, curiosity, conservatism, hedonism, connection to nature, anthropocentric environmental concerns, social justice, etc. Personal norms often differ according to membership in sociodemographic groups, such as age groups, gender dimensions, or formal education and access to knowledge.

Habits

Besides attitude, intention and motivation, habits are also a central factor determining behaviour. These are behaviour patterns that become automated through repeated performance with satisfactory results under similar circumstances. Convenience can lead to a habit, such as ease of access to a product or the way the product is prepared and consumed (Timpanaro & Cascone, 2022). Bourdieu defines habitus as a socialised and structuring structure and is the sum of an individual's behaviours, experiences, beliefs, convictions and dispositions. It is unconsciously structured by an individual's life experiences, upbringing and exposure to the rules and conditions of a field (Cusworth & Dodsworth, 2021). In this respect, habitus and attitude cannot be clearly distinguished as factors determining behaviour. However, the focus of the habitus is that it develops in practice, as it is the result of the individual's unreflective participation in a socially organised logic of practice (Onorati & d'Ovidio, 2022).

Trust, risk and uncertainty

Trust issues arise when a person contemplates or engages in risk-associated behaviour. Trust is shaped by factors that affect both the person trusting (trustor) and the person being trusted (trustee) and can be understood as consisting of three dimensions: ability, benevolence, and integrity (Mayer et al., 2006). People who make decisions under conditions of uncertainty and imperfect knowledge tend to be guided by trustworthy institutions.

Emotions

Emotions represent how people feel about something. It is an important behavioural category that is related to cognitive dissonance. Values and attitudes are necessary conditions, but are usually not sufficient to promote changes in behaviour. In this respect, emotions have a stronger influence on behaviour change (Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). Emotions are often under-estimated in models of behaviour change, as for example the models where they are defined as a mediator to attitudes but not as an independent behavioural factor (Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). This is also the case for Practice Theory where emotions inform what meaning is allocated to a practice, together with the factors (cultural) values, norms, desires (Kaiser & Burger, 2022).

Behavioural control (competences, skills, autonomy and materials)

In the TPB, perceived behavioural control is defined as the "perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour" (Ajzen, 1991). This specifically includes perceptions about the presence or absence of factors that may facilitate or hinder the behaviour (Sok et al., 2021). Factors include abilities, skills and resources, as well as perceptions about whether unforeseen and insurmountable obstacles will occur (Six, 2019). People who feel that they have the self-efficacy to perform a certain behaviour are more likely to perform that behaviour (Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017). Perceived behavioural control suggests that control over the execution of a behaviour depends on factors such as training, learning, previous experiences, whether they have been able to overcome obstacles or deficiencies, and whether they expect support from others when needed (Ajzen, 2020). The two sub-dimensions of perceived behavioural control are 'ability' - the perception of whether the person is able to perform the behaviour - and 'autonomy' - the degree of perceived self-determination in making decisions related to the behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010). The role of autonomy for satisfaction is highlighted by Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2012). The theory differentiates three types of motivation: Intrinsic motivation involves fully autonomous behaviour, with values and beliefs being completely internalized and where the motivation is perceived to fully originate from the individual self (de Lauwere et al., 2022). Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand is driven by external pressure and not perceived as an autonomous behaviour (Deci & Ryan, 2012). Practice theory differentiates between competences and materials as behavioural factors that both can be put into relation to behavioural control.

Competences include the skills and knowledge needed for performing a practice (Kaiser & Burger, 2022). Materials are the physical elements related to performing a practice such as technology, machinery, or infrastructure (Kaiser & Burger, 2022).

Citizen-consumer

Food consumers equals food citizens. This route relates to *consumer* groups that are associated with a huge degree of “food awareness” and political or ethical motives (de Bakker & Dagevos, 2012). Consumers are defined as *citizens* when they are able to embrace a sustainable and moral concept of consumption focused on collective well-being. In postmodernity and its context of globalization, there is a higher need of consumers to take responsibility for the planet and there is higher awareness of global implications of their choices (Ricci et al., 2016). The citizen-consumer is a consumer that can take influence over decisions regarding sustainable nutrition (Leresche, 2018). Various studies have identified a gap between consumers’ attitudes and the actual behaviour, which is often referred to as the so-called citizen-consumer gap (de Bakker & Dagevos, 2012).

Consumer

We refer to people who consume food as consumers. Food consumption includes the purchase, consumption, but also the waste of food.

Driver

“The term driver in a food system context still has somewhat of an elusive quality, which warrants a more differentiated look at the qualities of driving forces at play. It makes a big difference, for instance, between taking a systemic or an actor-centric perspective on the food system” (Kretschmer et al., 2022, p. 2).

“The main drivers are socio-demographic (ageing, depopulation, social perception of the profession), economic (free market, industrialization), political (lack of adequate of national and European policies) and environmental (climate change, forest fires)” (Dinis & Simões, 2021, p. 1).

“The global food system, especially food production, is a major driver of global environmental change” (Pereira et al., 2020, p. 2).

“The plurality of driving forces affecting the evolution of the agricultural landscape can be explained by the complex nature of the system. Among the prevailing proximate driving forces, urban/tourist development, removal of landscape elements, and intensification of agriculture, as well as rural development policy schemes (including agri-environmental measures), can be mentioned, with varying degrees of influence. At the same time, a series of underlying driving forces has been identified, under various categories, e.g., driving forces like real estate market and market growth, technological modernization in land management, as well as cultural driving forces such as public attitudes and values and individual/household behavior” (Vlahos, 2020).

Farmers

We refer to those individuals as farmers who produce crop or livestock products using *farming practices* (primary production). In addition to this, farmers may also process products or produce other services (e.g. agro-tourism) or products (e.g. energy). Farmers do not necessarily have to be the owners of a farm. We consider farmers to be the people who make key decisions regarding the choice and implementation of *farming practices*.

Farming practices

Farming practices include all aspects that define the **management** of agricultural land such as the decision what crop to grow, what animals to keep, what production system to choose, what external inputs to apply, what soil management strategies to choose, etc. Farming practices can also be detached from land. This is the case when animals are kept that are supplied with feed from outside the farm or when crop production does not take place on soils (soilless culture).

Farming system

We define Farming System as the system, which includes all activities and actors related to the implementation of *farming practices*. This also includes activities and actors that operate outside the farm boundary and directly or indirectly influence the choice and implementation of *farming practices*.

Food system

“The food system is defined as the production of food within a value chain comprising several stages” (Salavisa et al., 2021, p. 1). It comprises all activities and actors related to the production, processing, packaging, distribution, retail and consumption of food, and the outcomes of these activities that affect food security, social welfare and environmental welfare (Kump & Fikar, 2021, p. 2; Salavisa et al., 2021, p. 1). It includes various actors and a complex web of activities, outcomes and drivers, encompassing not only the food and agriculture sectors, but also the social norms and cultures in which those activities are embedded (Kretschmer et al., 2022, p. 1).

Interventions

An intervention is the “act of creating alternative distribution mechanisms that respond to perceived deficiencies within the current system”. It “can serve as an implicit critique of the regime and change consumers’ awareness of and attitude toward food and the conventional food industry” (Kump & Fikar, 2021, p. 9).

We differentiate between behavioural and systemic interventions in relation to who/what is targeted: Behavioural interventions are targeting the actors that are supposed to change their behaviours (e.g. farmers). “Behaviour change interventions’ can be defined as coordinated sets of activities designed to change specified behaviour patterns.” (Michie et al., 2011).

Systemic interventions target systems by focusing on groups of people and their relationships. In the research led by ENFASYS, interventions will be highlighted through CLDs.

Leverage

Where can push exert pressure to use something that you already have in order to achieve something new or better the power to influence results. Levers combine policy, technology, education and awareness-raising, dietary shifts and financial/economic mechanisms.

Leverage points are defined as “domains for interventions that can result in observable changes within a system” (Manlosa et al., 2019, p. 530). Leverage points are places in future regime shifts where either push a failing system into tipping or intervening to facilitate transformation of the system (Pereira et al., 2020).

Use and management of biodiversity is a major lever of sustainability in farming systems (Martinelli et al., 2022)). “Crop diversification is one of the levers that can contribute to increasing within-field biodiversity which supports ecosystem services and helps to close nutrient cycles allowing to substitute for chemical inputs as well as supporting more diversified agrifood systems at large” (Messean et al., 2021, p. 475). “Concrete leverage points for governing agricultural transitions towards sustainability include public funding of sustainable agriculture, reforming counterproductive incentive systems such as the EU Common Agricultural Policy; fostering institutions for knowledge exchange and learning as well as knowledge co-production; collaborative governance mechanisms; educational programs on sustainable agriculture; rural development policies as well as local or alternative food governance networks” (Melchior & Newig, 2021, p. 12).

“Levers for furthering the adoption of various types of innovative integrated crop and livestock systems include both pull and push factors that could disrupt the existing agricultural regime and destabilize locked-in specialized high input agriculture, practices and associated value chains. Pull factors are conditions and changes in the landscape and regime that create a need for innovation (top-down processes). Push factors are bottom-up processes that emerge from the niche context, i.e., local knowledge, social, and institutional changes, to supply and support new technologies and can address top-down needs. Push factors alone are often not enough to disrupt the socio-technical regime and bring about practice change, but are often critical in testing and refining technologies to be ready for adoption should other drivers sufficiently favor a shift in practice” (Garrett et al. 2020, p. 8).

Levers

Levers are strategic principles that are meant to unlock a blocked situation. Levers are points in the system where a strategically tailored intervention can incentivize farmers moving to and staying in SFS and create positive lasting change. “Localized agrifood systems, particularly geographical indications, are a lever for evolving towards sustainable agriculture” (Millet & Casabianca, 2019, p. 1).

(Systemic) Lock-ins

Lock-ins are persistent systemic factors leading to undesirable patterns of behaviour. They are aspects of the system that generate reinforcing feedback of incumbent systemic structures and dynamics that prevent change such as the adoption of sustainable farming practices (Weituschat et al., 2022, p. 2203). Lock-ins and transitions result from the interlinking of a variety of mechanisms, and solutions to these lock-ins are therefore often context-specific.

A lock-in phenomenon arises when a set of intertwined barriers hinder the evolution of a system or the adoption of an innovation into this system, to the point that the effort to change the system/adopt an innovation is too high for one actor independently. Systems may remain locked-in (i.e. evolving only within a limited range of options that don't imply a significant system reconfiguration) until an impactful change happens within or around the system, opening new opportunities or making usual practices and norms obsolete, inappropriate or irrelevant. To actively overcome locked-in situations, barriers must be addressed in a coordinated way (Antier et al., 2021) and involve multiple actors (Antier et al., 2021; Vanloqueren & Baret, 2008).

Farmers are challenged by multiple lock-ins (structural, economic and political) that prevent them moving to more SFS. “Structural lock-in effects are factors beyond the control of individual communities, such as moral codes, religion, and tradition. Economic lock-ins are related to the consequences of economic capital, such as the impact of globalization and capitalism on lifestyle” (Stotten et al., 2021, p. 125) Lock-ins and windows of opportunity may arise at farming system level, the value-chain level and governance level.

Table 1 Overview of lock-ins

Dimensions of lock-in	Description
Technological	Infrastructure and (applied) know-how organised around existing technologies and practices
Economic	Existing economies of scale, sunk investments creating costs and benefits biased towards current technologies and practices
Institutional	Existing regulations, standards, and policy networks create an uneven playing field biased towards the status quo
Political	Vested interests and power relations that favour the status quo
Social	Existing alignments, relations and social capital between social groups
Cognitive	Routines and mindsets that “blind” actors to (the benefits of) other alternatives

Source: Adapted from Geels (2019)

(Weituschat et al. 2022, p. 2205)

Policy Design

Public policies

“Public policies are the result of efforts made by governments to alter aspects of behaviour—both of their own agents and of society at large—in order to carry out some end or purpose. To do so, they are comprised of complex arrangements of policy goals and policy means” (Howlett & Rayner, 2018, p. 1). A public policy thus defines a consistent course of action designed to respond to an issue or problem identified by the government as requiring action or reform. It is implemented by a public body (ministry, agency, etc.), although elements may be delegated to other bodies. Public policies are linked to governments’ programs, the related strategic planning, and are often given a formal framework through legislation and regulations, and are put into practice through a defined course of action with its related activities. It is, as necessary, funded from the state budget (OECD A to Z of Public Governance Terms).

Policy design

Policy design is an “activity conducted by a number of policy actors in the hope of *improving* policymaking and policy outcomes through the accurate anticipation of the consequences of government actions and the articulation of specific courses of action to be followed (...) It is the effort to more or less systematically develop efficient and effective policies through the application of knowledge about policy means gained from experience and reason, to the development and adoption of courses of action that are likely to succeed in attaining their desired goals or aims” (Howlett & Rayner, 2018). For the ENFASYS project, we consider shortcomings in earlier policy design for agricultural and food policies (e.g. De Schutter, 2019) and strive to adopt a co-designing approach with stakeholders.

This approach follows longstanding debates about farmers' knowledge, dialogue between equals (e.g. "Farmer First" approaches developed by Chambers (1985) and pursued by Thompson and Scoones (2009)) as well as food sovereignty debates and the right of people to define their own food systems (e.g.,). In the above definition, the term "policy actors" is thus replaced by "stakeholders", where these include representatives of all stakeholder groups identified in the case initiatives.

Policy Mix

In its most basic form, policy mixes are implicitly or explicitly defined as the combination of several policy instruments, leading to a narrow definition where policy mix equals interacting instruments aimed at achieving objectives in a dynamic setting. The narrow definition has been criticized as referring to an "instrument mix" rather than a policy mix and leading scholars suggest to adopt an extended definition allowing to better grasp its complexity. For the ENFASYS project, we rely on this broader definition of policy mix as outlined by Rogge and Reinhardt (2016). A policy mix then is a combination of several main building blocks (elements; policy processes; characteristics; dimensions). Elements comprise the policy strategy with its objectives and principal plans for achieving them; and the instrument mix with its interacting policy instruments. Policy processes are composed of policy making and policy implementation. Characteristics describe the mix in terms of consistency, coherence, congruence, as well as credibility and comprehensiveness. Dimensions delineate the policy mix, examples are policy field, governance level, geography, time. This translates into a three-level approach of policy mixes, with the first level referring to policy objectives, the second to policy instruments and the third to instrument calibrations (Grohmann & Feindt, 2023). *See below for descriptions of the different components of policy mixes mentioned here.*

Policy Strategy

A policy strategy is a combination of policy objectives (*see below*) and the principal plans (*see below*) for achieving them (emphasis is thus on the output – the end and means – of the strategy process) (Rogge & Reichardt, 2016).

Policy objective(s)

As "manifestations of cognitive assumptions and normative beliefs underlying a policy as fundamental ideas linked to expectations, purposes and ends" (Grohmann & Feindt, 2023, p. 3), policy objective(s) are rather "large", "overarching" (e.g. mitigating climate change; greening the economy; ...) and tend to be substantiated by long-term targets with quantified ambition levels (e.g. x % reduction of greenhouse gases until 2050). Besides content-oriented objectives, they can also contain process and learning objectives. Also, policy objectives may be either sectoral or cross-sectoral, thus affecting a single policy field/sector or several at once (Rogge and Reichardt 2018). Sectoral objectives refer to goals that are designed to achieve desired outcomes of policymaking in a specific sector whereas cross-cutting objectives refer to impacts of policymaking across policy sectors (Grohmann & Feindt, 2023).

Principal (policy) plans

Principal policy plans are plans for achieving the policy objectives. Plans outline the general path to take for attaining the objectives and include framework conventions, guidelines, strategic action plans, roadmaps, etc., and typically surpass electoral cycles (inherent long-term perspective) (e.g. EU Strategic Energy Technology Plan, German Energy Concept, ...) (Rogge & Reichardt, 2016).

In the sense of this definition, the CAP is a Policy Strategy as it is = objectives + plan. However, the CAP (as well as the CFP) are legislative frameworks comprising established instruments, whereas the F2F strategy is a strategic communication, which sets out a roadmap for policy actions and initiatives (both legislative and non-legislative) that are not all in place yet (EEA 2022).

Policy Instruments

Policy Instruments are concrete tools to achieve the policy objectives. They are tools or techniques of governance that address policy problems, introduced by a governing body to achieve policy objectives, thereby translating plans of action (principal policy plans). Policy instruments are usually associated with specific goals describing their intended effect on achieving the overarching policy objectives (Rogge & Reichardt, 2016).

Policy instruments also need **calibration** (*see below*), the most important being instrument type (*see below*) and instrument design features/characteristics (*see below*) (Rogge & Reichardt, 2016). Some authors also stress the importance of more precise calibration (going beyond type and design feature) (cf. Grohmann and Feindt (2023) *and below*).

For a list of policy instruments relevant to food and corresponding policy acts with reference to Europe, see Galli et al. (2020).

Instrument type

Regarding instrument types, various taxonomies have been established in literature of different fields. A classic approach distinguishes between the means by which policy instruments try to change actor behavior, via ‘sticks’ (regulation), ‘carrots’ (incentives), and ‘sermons’ (information) (Bemelmans-Videc et al., 2011).

For the purpose of ENFASYS, we try to approach instrument type classification in a basic and at the same time encompassing way in order to have at hand a practical, stakeholder-accessible and -usable set rather than losing focus in a more complex, theoretical debate about different ways to approach instrument types. In consequence, we rely on the following, well-founded classification recently used by Bager et al. (2020) as they include commonly-accepted, four broad types of instruments, also referred to as “substantive instruments” because they directly affect the delivery of public goods and services (Howlett 2008, Mukherjee 2021): informational; cooperative and supportive; economic and market-based; and regulatory. Associated with the instrument types is their respective means by which they try to change actor behavior, as well as the degree of state intervention required. The development and implementation of these substantive policy instruments are influenced by a second category of policy instruments, namely “procedural” policy instruments. These refer to the management of state-societal interactions to assure support for government aims as well as to governments’ own processes of administration, thus concerning governments’ internal actions related to policymaking processes (Howlett 2008, Mukherjee 2021). Procedural policy instruments include “tools related to government’s design and implementation of network management mechanisms and public participation, activities linked to the delivery of organizational services such as the formation of advisory committees to regulatory agencies, and policy processes more generally, such as the creation of public information commissions, government data portals and repositories, and judicial review processes” (Mukherjee 2021, p. 312-313).

Table 3: Classification of policy instruments according to Bager et al. (2020, p.7)

Policy instrument	Means through which the policy instrument is applied
<i>Informational</i>	Campaigns, symbols, labels, data, research.
<i>Cooperative and supportive</i>	Roundtables, certification, agreements, transfers, mediation.
<i>Economic and market-based</i>	Taxes, subsidies, tradable permits, tariffs, user charges, rebates, compensation, offsets.
<i>Regulatory</i>	Standards, bans, prohibitions, limits, permits, licenses, mandates.

When using the MLP framework, different policy instruments may be useful at different levels and stages of the transition. Kanger et al. (2020) identified examples of instruments for different intervention points within the MLP framework.

Table 4: Policy intervention points for sustainability transitions (EEA 2023, p. 28)

Intervention point	Policy rationale	Examples of instruments
Niche stimulation	Stimulate the emergence of diverse forms of innovations (technical, social, nature-based, etc.) in niches through shielding, nurturing, learning and expectations	R&D funding schemes and support for demonstration projects, tax exemptions, education policies and training programmes, etc.
Niche acceleration	Upscale, replicate and institutionalise niche practices and align niches with each other	Incubators, standards and labels, promotion of entrepreneurship, advisory services, subsidies, public procurement, venture capital, etc.
Regime destabilisation	Phase out unsustainable practices and weaken the position of incumbent regime actors	Subsidy removal and reforms, technology bans, carbon trading, pollution taxes, removal of tax deductions for incumbents, etc.
Repercussions of regime destabilisation	Anticipate and manage the broader social and economic disruption associated with sustainability transitions	Creative labour adjustment programmes, compensation schemes, education to support reskilling and unemployment, etc.
Coordination of multi-regime interaction	Ensure that input-output relations and multi-regime linkages are complementary and mutually supportive	Cross-cutting strategies that bring together siloed policies areas; processes such as impact assessments
Landscape tilt	Alter broader framework conditions and give direction to innovation and socio-technical systems change	Overarching strategic frameworks, such as the European Green Deal, long-term goals and roadmaps (e.g. 2050 targets, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs))

Design features / characteristics of policy mixes / calibrations

Design features or characteristics are used to assess the integration of policy mixes. This matters because integration and correspondence across elements is “required if policy goals are to be integrated successfully with policy means” (Howlett and Rayner 2018, p.394). The main design features are consistency, coherence, and congruence. Empirical studies on the evolution of policy mixes have shown that these features are especially weakly represented in policies that have evolved over a long time (Howlett and Rayner 2018) as is the case for the CAP in very exemplary way (e.g. (Daugbjerg & Feindt, 2017)). In more recent works, the concept of “calibrations” has been put forward to move from the approaches of design features or characteristics to a more precise analysis of the degree to which a policy instrument contributes to the policy objectives (and affects other policy goals or policy sectors) (e.g. Grohmann and Feindt 2023). Grohmann and Feindt define calibration as the “concrete adjustments of the policy instrument settings” and propose four analytical dimensions: stringency (relative depth of intervention of an instrument through its calibration); specificity (indicates the tailoring and target orientation of the instrument settings); flexibility (level to which target populations can accommodate the execution of an instrument to their particular circumstances); temporality (temporal elements of policy instrument implementation, e.g. timing of entry into force, phase-in and phase-out periods, payout periods) (Daugbjerg & Feindt, 2017; Grohmann & Feindt, 2023).

Consistency

Consistency is “the ability of multiple policy tools to reinforce rather than undermine each other in the pursuit of policy goals” (Howlett & Rayner 2018, p. 394).

Coherence

Coherence is “the ability of multiple policy goals to co-exist with each other and with instrument norms in a logical fashion” (Howlett & Rayner 2018, p. 394).

Congruence

Congruence is “ability of goals and instruments to work together in a unidirectional or mutually supportive fashion as important measures of optimality in policy mixes following this integrative logic” (Howlett & Rayner 2018, p. 394).

Dimensions delineating policy mixes

Examples of dimensions delineating policy mixes are policy field, governance level, geography, and time. These dimensions need to be taken into account when (co-)designing policy mixes to avoid creating ahistorical, context-detached policies, with, in consequence inefficient and unsatisfactory implementation in practice. This means that the historical context, implicated governance levels, the wider natural, economic and social context of the cases, as well as the temporal evolution of the existing policy mixes addressing or influencing the case, need to be analyzed and findings considered during policy design.

Policy fields / Policy areas

Due to the complexity of food systems, both in terms of the multitude of implicated actor types, as well as food supply chain activities and broader activities societal domains and interrelations between these, public policies stem from various policy areas; especially agricultural policies, environmental policies, trade policies and market regulation, fiscal and social policies, food safety, as well as education, development, research and public health. Poor collaboration between / integration of these policy areas is a challenge especially for addressing themes that are inherently multidisciplinary like agricultural and food systems. (IPES-Food 2019).

Governance levels and exchange between them

In agricultural and food policy, EU level bodies provide the framing texts, the individual EU member nations apply these with more or less room for interpretation (e.g. coercive to voluntary). At EU level, responsibilities are shared by several DGs. To illustrate the complexity, for the Farm2Fork strategy, the following directorates-general were involved (and others might potentially be affected or influenced by the strategy):

Figure 11: Directorates general involved in Farm2Fork strategy (EEA 2023, p. 77)

Due to their multidisciplinary character, agricultural and/or food system policies are divided between responsible organisms, for example between ministries at the level of nation-states or between DGs at the level of the European Commission. It should also be noted that an additional challenge is that the responsibilities are not split / organized uniformly, neither when comparing EU-level and nation-states-level nor when comparing nation-states, which means that the responsible organism for a specific policy area is not the same one in each nation-state. Also, several policy areas may be assembled in one ministry and here again, this is not uniform between member states. Also, responsibilities for specific policy areas are reorganized with time, meaning that the responsibility for a specific area may switch from one to another ministry.

Given the gaps of knowledge -, learning - and best practice sharing between governance levels, especially from bottom to top, EU policymakers are disconnected from experiences from the ground that could be learned from and help redirecting EU-level policies towards being more supportive (IPES-Food 2019). By co-designing policy mixes with stakeholders from ground cases and subsequent upscaling towards informing public policy making at EU-level, ENFASYS contributes to filling these gaps.

Producers

Producers of food are “key agents of change in the food system, whether they are farmers or fishers” (SAPEA, 2020, p. 105). “There are two different kinds of producers in food system, the domestic and the foreign. Domestic producers are all subject to the same legal order and they are particularly sensitive to domestic policies for sustainability” (SAPEA, 2020, p. 107).

Stakeholder

A stakeholder is any institution, group or individual who i) has the power/ability to make a real change towards the desired transition, (ii) holds valuable information or knowledge for the issue at hand, and/or (iii) is directly/indirectly affected by the planning and implementation of the desired transition. Different types of stakeholders are described in *Actors*.

System

"A system is understood as a complex of parties that establish relationships with each other, and the behaviour of each is characterized by the connection in which it is involved" (Fassio et al., 2022, p. 2). (Agricultural) land systems are framed as socio-ecological systems having a level of resilience owing to negative systemic feedbacks that abate pressures of change (Fassio et al., 2022).

Systemic factors

Systemic factors are those constraining and motivating effects on individuals actions of social dynamics of the systems or social structures in which actors are positioned. These systems consist out of social relationships between different actors, that constrain, enable and motivate actors depending on their position in various ways (materially, cognitively, spiritually, ...). Through this ‘structured’ agency actors set collectively in motion dynamics reproducing or changing the existing social relationships, and thus the systemic factors over time. Persistent systemic factors leading to undesirable patterns of behavior are called lock-ins. The term system may seek to capture phenomena at a micro-level, such as the family farm, at a meso-level like an innovation hub or a value chain, but also macro-level phenomena like global capitalism or the European Monetary Union.

Transition

Transitions is a “gradual, continuous process[es] of change where the structural character of a society (or a complex sub-system of society) transforms. [It is] not uniform, and nor is the transition process deterministic; there are large differences in the scale of change and the period over which it occurs. Transitions involve a range of possible development paths, whose direction, scale and speed government policy can influence, but never entirely control” (Fassio et al., 2022; Rotmans et al., 2001, p. 16). A major focus of the sustainability transitions research field is to understand system dynamics in order to inform governance and policy (Loorbach et al., 2020). “Transition scholars investigate why and how socio-technical systems shift to more sustainable configurations” (Markard et al. 2012; in: Rohe et al. 2022, p. 83).

Transition processes include, but are not limited to, technical, political, market and cognitive dimensions (Dumont et al. 2020), and literature discussing them often focusses on macro- and meso-level processes (Weituschat et al. 2022).

“Sustainability transitions are fundamental, purposive changes to fulfil societally necessary functions more sustainably” (Weituschat et al., 2022, p. 2204). They are "understood as long-term processes of fundamental and far-reaching regime change from a less sustainable to a more sustainable state, where socio-technical regimes refer to co-evolved dominant industries or otherwise institutionalised practices, characterised by “lock-in”, such that the different regime elements (e.g., policies, practices, technologies, knowledge, or values) stabilise each other, making change a challenging task” (Melchior and Newig 2021, p. 2).

Transformation

Transformation is an extreme case where profound change alters the distribution of rights and responsibilities and visions of development across society Pelling (2011, p. 73-74). With respect to food systems, Weber et al. (2020, p. 12) define “transformation as encompassing both social and technological innovation and seeing a strong role for social movements and civil society”, whereas transition “[describes] a rather controlled change process with less

emphasis on human agency, contestation, and deliberation”. Transformation in research is both used as metaphor and an analytical concept (Feola, 2015).

“Sustainability transformations are profound changes in cognitive, relational, structural and/or functional aspects of social-technical-ecological systems aiming at new interactions among them and at qualitative and/or physical outcomes leading to more sustainable pathways” (Patterson et al. 2017; in Young et al. 2022, p. 67).

“Transformations towards sustainability via conflict transformation address issues of desired change across four levels: personal, relational, structural and cultural” (Young et al. 2022, p. 69).

Value chain

The second level of interest in ENFASYS project is the value-chain level, which encompasses activities, actors and resources from primary production to the other value chain stages, incl. consumption.

Following Melchior & Newig (2021, p. 2) we can define a **value chain** as follows: “The value chain describes the full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the intermediary phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and the input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use”. “A Global Value Chain (GVC) is a chain of activities which are divided among multiple firms in different geographical locations”. “The central concern in GVC analysis is tracing where the value added is contributed and how its distribution can be explained” (Gradin, 2016, p. 4). “Each contemporary global value chain can be divided into two segments, a segment in which all value added activities are centred on the production of the good or service, and a segment in which efforts to reach the final customer or user results in increased value added. The approximate moment or place where the focus of attention moves from production to the market is called here the ‘focal point’. It cuts the global value chain into an upstream segment centred on production and a downstream segment centred on the market” (Lunati & Organisation ... 2008, p. 47). At value-chain level, following Therond et al. (2017), we distinguish four different types of social-economic settings that influence the development and functioning of farming systems: globalized commodity-based food systems, circular economies, alternative food systems and integrated landscape approaches.

Food chain is “covering food production, transport, distribution, marketing and consumption” (Farm ... 2020, p. 7).

Food system contains “all elements and activities that relate to production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food. Two end-points of the global food system are: final consumption (healthy diets) and production (sustainable food production) (EAT-Lancet ... 2023).

Alternative food networks usually refers to initiatives that aim to directly link producers and consumers, predominately at the local scale. Typical examples of alternative food networks include farmers’ markets, food box schemes, and food cooperatives (Kump & Fikar 2021, p. 2)

10 References

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